
SUPPORTING SCHEMA AND DATA PROVENANCE UNDER DATABASE EVOLUTION WITH PROV TEMPLATE

–SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL–

SPECIFICATION OF SMO/DMO OPERATORS WITH PROV TEMPLATE

1 Introduction

This specification defines in detail the patterns for capturing both schema and data provenance, resulting from the application of Schema Modification Operators (SMO) and Integrity Constraints Modification Operators (ICMOs), with PROV. These patterns also come with additional patterns for capturing data modification operations (DMO), needed to apply some SMOs. The main objective of this specification is to provide a tool for capturing/archiving machine-interpretable and detailed interoperable metadata describing database evolution driven by SMOs and ICMOs.

This document has been organized into three main parts:

- Section 2 provides an insight into the information required for the accurate understanding of this specification such as the notational conventions used throughout the document (Section 2.1), or the description of the structure for the pattern's explanations (Section 2.2).
- Section 3 shows a table that associates each pattern's identifier with the page where it is explained.
- Sections 4, 5 and 6 provide a systematic explanation of each pattern classified by the addressed DMO, SMO or ICMO, respectively.

2 Before reading

As we see this document as the reference specification for our proposal for automatically capturing both schema and data provenance with PROV distinguishing among the different SMOs and ICMOs, each pattern has been written in a self-contained way. A reader who reads all the patterns sequentially from the first to the last will find similar explanations, even repeated ones, in several patterns. We have preferred to make the reader suffer this small inconvenience, instead of running the risk that an occasional reader of a particular pattern loses part of the explanations that are discussed elsewhere.

We assume that the reader is familiar with the following data modification operations (DMO): *INSERT* and *DELETE*, with the following schema modification operators (SMO): *ADD_{table}*, *DEL_{table}*, *ADD_{column}* and *COPY_{table}*, and with the following Integrity constraints modification operator (ICMO): *ADD_{primaryKey}*. Readers unfamiliar with these operators are encouraged to read [1, 2, 3, 4] or a detailed and formal presentation of the operators and their capabilities.

Likewise, we assume that the reader is knowledgeable about both the PROV data model (PROV-DM) [5], to represent provenance information, and the PROV template approach [6], for designing provenance. If this is not the case, she/he is referred to [5] and [6], respectively.

2.1 Notational conventions

The PROV templates throughout this document are represented following the PROV graph conventions given in [7].

We also use *qualified names* (e.g., `prov:value`) in accordance to PROV-DM [5]. In compliance with PROV-DM, we note that a *qualified name* can be mapped to an Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI) [8] by concatenating the IRI associated

with the prefix (e.g., `prov`) and the local part (e.g., `value`). Every *qualified name* with a prefix refers to the namespace of the prefix. The following namespaces and prefixes are used throughout this document.

prefix	namespace IRI	definition
tmpl	https://openprovenance.org/tmpl#	The prov-template namespace
var	http://openprovenance.org/var#	The namespace for template variables
prov	http://www.w3.org/ns/prov#	The PROV namespace
xsd	http://www.w3.org/2000/10/XMLSchema#	XML Schema namespace
o2p	http://uml2prov.unirioja.es/ns/o2p#	SMO2PROV namespace regarding operator execution
sch2p	http://uml2prov.unirioja.es/ns/sch2p#	SMO2PROV namespace regarding schema aspects
d2p	http://uml2prov.unirioja.es/ns/d2p#	SMO2PROV namespace regarding data aspects
bitemp	http://uml2prov.unirioja.es/ns/bitemp#	SMO2PROV namespace regarding bitemporal data

Table 1. Prefix and Namespaces used in this specification

More specifically, we note that we consider specific namespaces intended for use with facets defined in the PROV family of documents. These namespaces define (1) new categories of entities from a schema evolution perspective and (2) further attributes for extending PROV-DM from the schema evolution perspective. In the following, the keyword “MUST” in this document is to be interpreted as described in [9]. Concretely:

Namespace <http://uml2prov.unirioja.es/ns/o2p#>. It defines new attributes referred to the execution of the SMO/DMO operator itself. We suggest the use of `o2p` as a prefix for this namespace. More specifically:

- `o2p:executed`. This attribute is the information regarding whether the operator has been executed. The value associated with this attribute MUST be a boolean (a value of type `xsd:boolean`). It is allowed in PROV Entities.
- `o2p:instruction`. This attribute is the executed instruction. The value associated with this attribute MUST be a string (a value of type `xsd:string`). It is allowed in PROV Entities.

Namespace <http://uml2prov.unirioja.es/ns/sch2p#>. It defines new categories of entities and further attributes referred to schema aspects. We suggest the use of `sch2p` as a prefix for this namespace. More specifically:

Categories of entity

- `sch2p:Schema`. A database schema is denoted by `sch2p:Schema`.
- `sch2p:Table`. A table is denoted by `sch2p:Table`.
- `sch2p:Column`. A column in a table is denoted by `sch2p:Column`.

Further Attributes

- `sch2p:schemaName`. This attribute is the name of a database schema. The value associated with this attribute MUST be a string (a value of type `xsd:string`). It is allowed in PROV Entities.
- `sch2p:tableName`. This attribute is the name of a table. The value associated with this attribute MUST be a string (a value of type `xsd:string`). It is allowed in PROV Entities.
- `sch2p:columnName`. This attribute is the name of a column. The value associated with this attribute MUST be a string (a value of type `xsd:string`). It is allowed in PROV Entities.
- `sch2p:typeName`. This attribute is the name of the type of a column. The value associated with this attribute MUST be a string (a value of type `xsd:string`). It is allowed in PROV Entities.

Namespace <http://uml2prov.unirioja.es/ns/d2p#>. It defines a new category of entity and further attributes referred to data aspects. We suggest the use of `d2p` as a prefix for this namespace. More specifically:

Category of entity

- `d2p:Value`. A value of a column in a row is denoted by `d2p:Value`.

Further Attributes

- `d2p:columnValue`. This attribute is the concrete value of a column in a row. The value associated with this attribute **MUST** be a primitive datatype. It is allowed in PROV Entities.
- `d2p:rowID`. This attribute is the specific row identifier. The value associated with this attribute **MUST** be a positive integer (a value of type `xsd:positiveInteger`). It is allowed in PROV Entities.

Namespace <http://uml2prov.unirioja.es/ns/bitemp#>. It defines new attributes referred to bitemporal information (both valid and transactional). These attributes are associated with `Activities` and `Entities` because we consider bitemporal information very useful not only from a provenance but also from the schema evolution point of view. Nevertheless, these attributes are optional and the user is free either to include them or using only the temporal attributes `tmpl:startTime` and `tmpl:endTime`. We suggest the use of `bitemp` as a prefix for this namespace. More specifically, the defined attributes are:

- `bitemp:startTransTime`.
- `bitemp:endTransTime`.
- `bitemp:startValidTime`.
- `bitemp:endValidTime`.

2.2 Structure of the patterns

We have structured the explanation of the defined patterns in the same six blocks: **Identifier**, **Syntax**, **Semantics**, **DMO/S-MO/ICMO's involved elements**, **Mapping to PROV**, and **Discussion**. See the explanation of each block below.

2.2.1 Identifier

Unique identifier of the DMO/SMO/ICMO pattern. It is an acronym that refers to the word 'DMO'/'SMO'/'ICMO' plus the character 'P-' (pattern) plus the identification of the concrete type of the operator. For example, the ADD_{table} SMO is referred to as $SMOP-ADD_{table}$.

2.2.2 Syntax

The SQL-like syntax of the DMO/SMO/ICMO pattern. In the case of SMOs, we have mainly based on the syntax given in [4]. More specifically, in the remainder, $R.C = \{c_1, \dots, c_n\}$ denotes the set of columns of table R and R_i specifies the version i of the table R . Whenever a SMO does not change the table's name but its columns or rows, we increment this version counter i [4]. The version counter is also incremented when applying an ICMO. Similarly, as every SMO/ICMO takes as input a schema and produces as output a new version of the same schema, we use V_j , to denote the source schema version, and V_{j+1} , to denote the target schema version.

2.2.3 Semantics

Each pattern semantics block will include a detailed description of its *key elements*. We remark that not all the identified *key elements* explicitly appear in the semantics (such as the source database schema, previous to the application of the SMO/ICMO, and target database schema, resulted from the application of the SMO/ICMO). More specifically, they are inferred from the semantics because they play an important role in the pattern. Additionally, certain *key elements* participate in the syntax and semantics by means of different alternatives, giving place to several nested elements. For example, in the ADD_{table} SMO syntax: $CREATE TABLE R(c_1, \dots, c_n)$, R participates both as the name of the table (R_{name}) to be created and the new table, itself (R).

In this section, we have represented in **dark blue** colour the database elements concerning schema information (schema versions, tables, columns, etc.), while **light blue** colour has been used to identify datadatabase data (columns' values).

2.2.4 DMO/SMO/ICMO's involved elements

This block will depict the elements involved in the DMO/SMO/ICMO's semantics that model the previous *key elements*. In addition, we provide a table, whose structure is illustrated below, that explains such *DMO/SMO/ICMO's involved elements*. Additionally, we assign a green label containing a numeric identifier to each involved element, which makes it easier its location in the image.

DMO/SMO/ICMO involved element	DMO/SMO/ICMO ID	Rationale
<i>Name of the element</i>	DMO/SMO/ICMO element	A description of the element and its role in the DMO/SMO/ICMO's semantics.

2.2.5 Mapping to PROV

This block contains the PROV template defined from the previous *DMO/SMO/ICMO's involved elements*, together with an explanation about its definition, that is, the *PROV elements, attributes, and PROV relations* defined from the *DMO/SMO/ICMO's involved elements*. We assign a numeric identifier to each *PROV element* that corresponds to the identifier of the *DMO/SMO/ICMO's involved element* from which it comes from. Additionally, each *relation* among PROV elements appearing in the PROV template is labelled with a letter that helps link such a relation with its description. The structure used to specify this block is the following:

PROV elements

DMO/SMO/ICMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
DMO/SMO/ICMO element / var:<identifier>	The explanation of the mapping between <i>DMO/SMO/ICMO element</i> and <i>PROV element</i> .	

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
PROV element	name of attribute / assigned value	The description of the meaning of the attribute and its value.

Note: Throughout this specification, we have included the attributes `bitemp:startTransTime/bitemp:startValidTime` and `bitemp:endTransTime/bitemp:endValidTime` of the SMO2PROV namespace, associated with `Activities` and `Entities` because we consider bitemporal information (both valid and transactional) very useful not only from a provenance but also from the schema evolution point of view. Nevertheless, these attributes are optional and the user is free either to include them or using only the temporal attributes `tmpl:startTime` and `tmpl:endTime`.

In some templates we have used the `tmpl:linked` attribute to avoid incorrect cartesian product when template instantiation, as described in [10] (for more information, the reader is referred to such reference).

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
PROV relation	Description of the relation.

Note: In PROV, two relationships of the form (B, `prov:used`, A) and (C, `prov:wasGeneratedBy`, B) may be enriched with (C, `prov:wasDerivedFrom`, A) to express the dependency of C on A. This structure is a provenance construction called *use-generate-derive triangle* [6] which explicitly connects a *generated* `prov:Entity` to a *used* `prov:Entity`. In the realm of this work, it may be applied in those templates in which a `prov:Entity` is *used* by a `prov:Activity`, and such a `prov:Activity` *generated* another `prov:Entity`. However, aiming at avoiding the overburden of the PROV template explanations with information that can be inferred, we have decided to include the relation `prov:wasDerivedFrom` only when the context of the pattern explicitly refers to such a derivation.

2.2.6 Discussion

Issues related to the representation of the DMOs/SMOs/ICMOs with PROV. Concretely, we will focus on the explanation and justification of our representation decisions together with alternative solutions (if any), and some questions that are likely to come up to the reader.

3 Index of patterns

DMOs representations		
Pattern identifier	Semantics	Page
<i>DMOP1</i>	<i>INSERT_{row}</i> - One row is inserted in table <i>R</i> .	8
<i>DMOP2</i>	<i>DELETE_{row}</i> - One or more rows are deleted from table <i>R</i> .	14

SMOs representations

Pattern identifier	Semantics	Page
<i>SMOP1</i>	<i>ADD_{table}</i> - A new table R is created. This operator takes a table name and a set of column definitions and creates an empty table with the specified name and schema [4].	19
<i>SMOP2</i>	<i>DROP_{table}</i> - The table R is dropped. This operator takes only a single parameter, the name of the table to be dropped [4].	24
<i>SMOP3</i>	<i>ADD_{column}</i> - A new column c is added to an existing table R_i . This operator takes as parameters the name of the table, the column definition of the new column, and optionally, a constant or function. The resulting table is R_{i+1} . If a constant is provided, this operator takes such a value as the row's value for the new column c [3]. If a function is provided, this operator applies it to each row in R_i to calculate the row's value for the new column c . The function receives all other column values of the row as parameters [4]. Otherwise, if neither the constant nor the function is provided, it assigns 'null' as the row's value for the new column c . The columns, columns's values as well as constraints in R_i remain the same in R_{i+1} .	29
<i>SMOP4</i>	<i>COPY_{table}</i> - A new table R is created as a duplicate of table T . The new additional table R is created with the same structure as the source table T . Additionally, this new table R should also contain the same data as the source table T [11]. Thus, this SMO includes the consecutive execution of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the SMO <i>CREATE_{table}</i> operator, needed to create the new table R, followed by • the corresponding DMO <i>INSERT_{row}</i> operation, needed to populate the new table R with the rows in the source table T. 	36
<i>SMOP5</i>	<i>MERGE_{tables}</i> - A new table R is created as the result of merging two given tables S and T along the row dimension, removing the original tables [4]. More specifically, this operator unions tuples of two tables into a target table. This operator takes as parameters the names of the original tables and the name of the resulting table [4]. Thus, this SMO includes the consecutive execution of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the SMO <i>CREATE_{table}</i> operator, needed to create the new table R, followed by • the corresponding DMO <i>INSERT_{row}</i> operation, needed to populate the new table R with the rows in the source tables S and T, and finished with • the SMO <i>DROP_{table}</i> operator used to remove the source tables S and T. 	43
<i>SMOP6</i>	<i>DECOMPOSE_{table}</i> - A table R is partitioned vertically into two (or one ¹) tables S and T and then it is removed. More specifically, <i>DECOMPOSE TABLE R INTO S (g₁,...,g_n) [, T, (g_j,...,g_m)</i> takes the name R of the original table, a pair of table name S and a set of column names s_i as specification of the first partition and optionally a second pair $T, (g_j, \dots, g_m)$ as specification of the second partition [4]. Thus, this SMO includes the consecutive execution of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the SMO <i>CREATE_{table}</i> operator, needed to create the new table(s) S (and T, if applicable), followed by • the corresponding DMO <i>INSERT_{row}</i> operations, needed to populate the new tables S (and T, if applicable) with the rows in the source table R, and finished with • the SMO <i>DROP_{table}</i> operator used to remove the source table R. <p>¹ See template's discussion.</p>	53

ICMOs representations

Pattern identifier	Semantics	Page
<i>ICMO1</i>	<i>ADD_{primaryKey}</i> - A primary key constraint <i>pk</i> is added to a table <i>R_i</i> . This operator takes a table name and a set of column names and creates a primary key constraint <i>pk</i> on such columns. Depending on the number of column names included in such a set, the primary key will be created on a single column or on multiple columns.	64

4 DMOs patterns

Pattern identifier	Semantics	Page
<i>DMO1</i>	<i>INSERT_{row}</i> - One row is inserted in table <i>R</i> .	8
<i>DMO2</i>	<i>DELETE_{row}</i> - One or more rows are deleted from table <i>R</i> .	14

Identifier DMO Pattern 1 (DMOPI) $INSERT_{row}$

Syntax

$INSERT$ INTO R (c_1, \dots, c_k) VALUES (v_1, \dots, v_k)

Semantics

One row is inserted in table R .

Key elements

<i>User</i>	The database user who performs the data modification operation $INSERT_{row}$.
<i>DMO operation</i>	The data modification operation whose application leads to the creation of a new row in table R . It takes as parameters: <i>Table</i> (R) See the <i>Table</i> element below. <i>Column</i> (c_k) See the <i>Column</i> element below. <i>Value</i> (v_k) The values to be inserted in the new row of the table must be provided. Each v_k refers to a data value to be assigned as value of a column c_k in <i>table</i> .
<i>Table</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through the element: <i>Table</i> (R) The table where the row will be inserted.
<i>Column</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through two different elements: <i>Column</i> (c_k) Each column c_k represents a column in the <i>table</i> involved in the insertion of the new row. <i>New column's value</i> (c_{v_k}) Each c_{v_k} represents a value that has been inserted in a <i>column</i> c_k of <i>table</i> R .

Database context

DMO involved element	DMO ID	Rationale
<i>User</i>	User 1	The database user who performs the schema modification operator $INSERT_{row}$. <i>Note:</i> for the shake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 1.
<i>DMO operation</i>	$INSERT_{row}$ 2	The data modification operation whose application leads to the creation of a new row in table R .
<i>Value</i>	v_k 3	Each v_k refers to a data value to be assigned as value of a column c_k in <i>table</i> .
<i>Table</i>	R 4	The table where the row will be inserted
<i>Column</i>	c_k 5	Each column of the <i>table</i> involved in the insertion of the new row.
<i>New column's value</i>	c_{v_k} 6	Each c_{v_k} represents a value that has been inserted in a <i>column</i> of <i>table</i> .

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Syntax: *INSERT INTO R (c₁...c_k) VALUES (v₁...v_k)*

Figure 1. Representation that models the semantics of *DMOP1*

Mapping to PROV

Figure 2. PROV template defined to represent semantics of *DMOP1* (Figure 1)

PROV elements

DMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
User 1	<code>prov:Agent 1 /</code> <code>var:user</code>	The User 1 bears the responsibility for the execution of the <code>INSERT_{row} 2</code> . To reflect this fact, the User 1 is mapped to a <code>prov:Agent</code> identified by <code>var:user</code> .
<code>INSERT_{row} 2</code>	<code>prov:Activity 2 /</code> <code>var:dmo</code>	The <code>INSERT_{row} 2</code> represents that the execution of an operator has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:dmo</code> .
<code>v_k 3</code>	<code>prov:Entity 3 /</code> <code>var:value</code>	<code>v_k 3</code> is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:value</code> .
<code>R 4</code>	<code>prov:Entity 4 /</code> <code>var:table</code>	<code>R 4</code> is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:table</code> .
<code>c_k 5</code>	<code>prov:Entity 5 /</code> <code>var:column</code>	Each <code>c_k 5</code> is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:column</code> .
<code>c_{vk} 6</code>	<code>prov:Entity 6 /</code> <code>var:newColumnName</code>	Each value <code>c_{vk} 6</code> is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:newColumnName</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
<code>var:dmo 2</code>	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>var:operatorName</code>	The value <code>var:operatorName</code> is the name of the operation <code>var:dmo 2</code> .
	<code>o2p:instruction /</code> <code>var:operationInstruction</code>	The value <code>var:operationInstruction</code> is the expression of the operation <code>var:dmo 2</code> .
	<code>o2p:executed /</code> <code>var:executed</code>	The value <code>var:executed</code> refers to whether the operator <code>var:dmo 2</code> has been executed or rolled back.
	<code>bitemp:startTransTime /</code> <code>var:startTransTime</code>	The <code>var:startTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction start time of <code>var:dmo 2</code> .
	<code>bitemp:endTransTime /</code> <code>var:endTransTime</code>	The <code>var:endTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction end time of <code>var:dmo 2</code> .
<code>var:value 3</code>	<code>prov:value /</code> <code>var:inputValue</code>	The value <code>var:inputValue</code> is the direct representation of <code>var:value 3</code> .
<code>var:table 4</code>	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>sch2p:table</code>	The value <code>sch2p:table</code> shows that <code>var:table 4</code> is a table.
	<code>sch2p:tableName /</code> <code>var:tableName</code>	The value <code>var:tableName</code> is the string with the name of the table <code>var:table 4</code> .
<code>var:column 5</code>	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>sch2p:column</code>	The value <code>sch2p:column</code> shows that <code>var:column 5</code> is a column.
	<code>sch2p:columnName /</code> <code>var:columnName</code>	The value <code>var:columnName</code> is the string with the name of the column <code>var:column 5</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:newColumnValue is a data value.		
	d2p:rowID / var:rowID	The var:rowID is the identifier of the tuple to which var:newColumnValue belongs.
	d2p:columnValue / var:columnValue	The value var:columnValue is the direct representation of var:newColumnValue .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:newColumnValue .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:startValidTime	The var:startValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:newColumnValue .
	bitemp:linked / var:value	Attribute needed to avoid incorrect cartesian product among var:newColumnValue .
	bitemp:linked / var:column	Attribute needed to avoid incorrect cartesian product among var:newColumnValue .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
prov:wasAssociatedWith	It is the assignment of responsibility to var:user for var:dmo.
prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:table by var:dmo.
prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:column by var:dmo.
prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:value by var:dmo.
prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:newColumnValue by var:dmo.
prov:specializationOf	var:newColumnValue is specialization of var:column.
prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of var:value resulting in var:newColumnValue.

Discussion

- The *key elements value* and *new column's value* correspond, respectively, to an operator's parameter and an operator's result. Both include the value to be stored/stored in a column of the new row. Thus, we somehow store repeated information. However, given that an operator might not be executed, we have decided to explicitly distinguish operator's parameters and the operator's results and separately represent them in the PROV template, ensuring us to register at least the operator's parameters in case the operator execution finally does not take place.
- We note that this operator also admits other syntaxis. This is the case of, for example, INSERT INTO R VALUES (v₁,...,v_n), considering that table R has n columns . This case would be represented in PROV Template in the same way exposed in this document so that the columns that participated in each INSERT_{row} operator are registered.
- Other syntaxis could be INSERT INTO R SELECT * FROM T, which allows insertion in a single instruction more than one row in the table (see Figure 3). In this case, the resulting PROV Template is similar to the one presented in Figure 2, but the var:value will include additional attributes including the information concerning the concrete column value of the source table T. Figure 4 depicts the transformation into PROV. Note that a var:value would be associated with its corresponding column of the corresponding table, associations created from the DMO/SMO that generates such a value.

Similarly, this template also covers the alternative syntaxis: INSERT INTO R (c₁,...,c_n) SELECT v₁,...,v_n FROM T [WHERE cond], where only some columns from one table are copied into another table, being optional the use of the WHERE clause to copy those rows that match the specified condition cond.

2

Syntax: *INSERT INTO R SELECT * FROM T*

Figure 3. Representation that models the semantics of *INSERT INTO R SELECT * FROM T*

Figure 4. PROV template defined to represent semantics of *INSERT INTO R SELECT * FROM T* (Figure 3)

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:value is a data value.		
	d2p:rowID / var:vRowID	The var:vRowID is the identifier of the tuple to which var:value belongs.
	d2p:columnValue / var:vColumnValue	The value var:vColumnValue is the direct representation of var:value .

Identifier DMO Pattern 2 (DMOP2) $DELETE_{row}$

Syntax

DELETE FROM R WHERE $cond$

Semantics

One or more rows are deleted from table R .

Key elements

<i>User</i>	The database user who performs the data modification operation $DELETE_{row}$.
<i>DMO operation</i>	The data modification operation whose application leads to the deletion of one or more rows in table R . It takes as parameters: <i>Table (R)</i> See the <i>Table</i> element below. <i>Condition ($cond$)</i> A <i>condition</i> $cond$ may be provided as parameter. It refers to the condition that must be met for the record(s) to be deleted. If the WHERE clause is omitted (and thus the <i>condition</i>), all records in the table will be deleted.
<i>Table</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through the element: <i>Table (R)</i> The table where the row or rows will be deleted.
<i>Column</i>	This element participates in the semantics through the element: <i>Deleted column's value (c_{vk})</i> Each c_{vk} represents a value of a deleted row of the <i>table</i> .

Database context

DMO involved element	DMO ID	Rationale
<i>User</i>	User 1	The database user who performs the schema modification operator $DELETE_{row}$. <i>Note:</i> for the shake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 5.
<i>DMO operation</i>	$DELETE_{row}$ 2	The data modification operation whose application leads to the deletion of one or more rows in table R .
<i>Condition</i>	$cond$ 3	The condition that must be meet for the record(s) to be deleted.
<i>Table</i>	R 4	The table where the row or rows will be deleted.
<i>Deleted column's value</i>	c_{vk} 5	Each c_{vk} represents a value of a deleted row of the <i>table</i> .

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Syntax: *DELETE FROM R* WHERE *cond*

Figure 5. Representation that models the semantics of *DMOP2*

Mapping to PROV

Figure 6. PROV template defined to represent semantics of *DMOP2* (Figure 5)

PROV elements

DMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
User 1	<code>prov:Agent 1 /</code> <code>var:user</code>	The User 1 bears the responsibility for the execution of the <code>INSERT_{row} 2</code> . To reflect this fact, the User 1 is mapped to a <code>prov:Agent</code> identified by <code>var:user</code> .
<code>DELETE_{row} 2</code>	<code>prov:Activity 2 /</code> <code>var:dmo</code>	The <code>DELETE_{row} 2</code> represents that the execution of an operator has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier.
<code>cond 3</code>	<code>prov:Entity 3 /</code> <code>var:cond</code>	<code>cond 3</code> is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:cond</code> .
<code>R 4</code>	<code>prov:Entity 4 /</code> <code>var:table</code>	<code>R 4</code> is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:table</code> .
<code>c_{vk} 5</code>	<code>prov:Entity 5 /</code> <code>var:deletedColumnValue</code>	Each value <code>c_{vk} 5</code> is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:deletedColumnValue</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
<code>var:dmo 2</code>	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>var:operatorName</code>	The value <code>var:operatorName</code> is the name of the operation <code>var:dmo 2</code> .
	<code>o2p:instruction /</code> <code>var:operationInstruction</code>	The value <code>var:operationInstruction</code> is the expression of the operation <code>var:dmo 2</code> .
	<code>o2p:executed /</code> <code>var:executed</code>	The value <code>var:executed</code> refers to whether the operator <code>var:dmo 2</code> has been executed or rolled back.
	<code>bitemp:startTransTime /</code> <code>var:startTransTime</code>	The <code>var:startTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction start time of <code>var:dmo 2</code> .
	<code>bitemp:endTransTime /</code> <code>var:endTransTime</code>	The <code>var:endTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction end time of <code>var:dmo 2</code> .
<code>var:cond 3</code>	<code>prov:value /</code> <code>var:condValue</code>	The value <code>var:condValue</code> is the direct representation of <code>var:cond 3</code> .
<code>var:table 4</code>	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>sch2p:table</code>	The value <code>sch2p:table</code> shows that <code>var:table 4</code> is a table.
	<code>sch2p:tableName /</code> <code>var:tableName</code>	The value <code>var:tableName</code> is the string with the name of the table <code>var:table 4</code> .
<code>var:deletedColumnValue 5</code>	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>d2p:value</code>	The value <code>d2p:value</code> shows that <code>var:deletedColumnValue 5</code> is a data value.
	<code>d2p:rowID /</code> <code>var:rowID</code>	The <code>var:rowID</code> is the identifier of the tuple to which <code>var:deletedColumnValue 5</code> belongs.
	<code>d2p:columnValue /</code> <code>var:columnValue</code>	The value <code>var:columnValue</code> is the direct representation of <code>var:newColumnValue 5</code> .
	<code>bitemp:endTransTime /</code> <code>var:endTransTime</code>	The <code>var:endTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction end time of <code>var:deletedColumnValue 5</code> .
	<code>bitemp:endValidTime /</code> <code>var:endValidTime</code>	The <code>var:endValidTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the valid end time of <code>var:deletedColumnValue 5</code> .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a prov:wasAssociatedWith	It is the assignment of responsibility to <code>var:user</code> for <code>var:dmo</code> .
b prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:table</code> by <code>var:dmo</code> .
c prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:cond</code> by <code>var:dmo</code> .
d prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that <code>var:deletedColumnValue</code> is not longer available for use.

Discussion

5 SMOs patterns

Pattern identifier	Semantics	Page
<i>SMOP1</i>	<i>ADD_{table}</i> - A new table <i>R</i> is created. This operator takes a table name and a set of column definitions and creates an empty table with the specified name and schema [4].	19
<i>SMOP2</i>	<i>DROP_{table}</i> - The table <i>R</i> is dropped. This operator takes only a single parameter, the name of the table to be dropped [4].	24
<i>SMOP3</i>	<i>ADD_{column}</i> - A new column <i>c</i> is added to an existing table <i>R_i</i> . This operator takes as parameters the name of the table, the column definition of the new column, and optionally, a constant or function. The resulting table is <i>R_{i+1}</i> . If a constant is provided, this operator takes such a value as the row's value for the new column <i>c</i> [3]. If a function is provided, this operator applies it to each row in <i>R_i</i> to calculate the row's value for the new column <i>c</i> . The function receives all other column values of the row as parameters [4]. Otherwise, if neither the constant nor the function is provided, it assigns 'null' as the row's value for the new column <i>c</i> . The columns, columns's values as well as constraints in <i>R_i</i> remain the same in <i>R_{i+1}</i> .	29
<i>SMOP4</i>	<i>COPY_{table}</i> - A new table <i>R</i> is created as a duplicate of table <i>T</i> . The new additional table <i>R</i> is created with the same structure as the source table <i>T</i> . Additionally, this new table <i>R</i> should also contain the same data as the source table <i>T</i> [11]. Thus, this SMO includes the consecutive execution of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the SMO <i>CREATE_{table}</i> operator, needed to create the new table <i>R</i>, followed by • the corresponding DMO <i>INSERT_{row}</i> operation, needed to populate the new table <i>R</i> with the rows in the source table <i>T</i>. 	36
<i>SMOP5</i>	<i>MERGE_{tables}</i> - A new table <i>R</i> is created as the result of merging two given tables <i>S</i> and <i>T</i> along the row dimension, removing the original tables [4]. More specifically, this operator unions tuples of two tables into a target table. This operator takes as parameters the names of the original tables and the name of the resulting table [4]. Thus, this SMO includes the consecutive execution of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the SMO <i>CREATE_{table}</i> operator, needed to create the new table <i>R</i>, followed by • the corresponding DMO <i>INSERT_{row}</i> operation, needed to populate the new table <i>R</i> with the rows in the source tables <i>S</i> and <i>T</i>, and finished with • the SMO <i>DROP_{table}</i> operator used to remove the source tables <i>S</i> and <i>T</i>. 	43
<i>SMOP6</i>	<i>DECOMPOSE_{table}</i> - A table <i>R</i> is partitioned vertically into two (or one ¹) tables <i>S</i> and <i>T</i> and then it is removed. More specifically, <i>DECOMPOSE TABLE R INTO S (g₁,...,g_n) [, T, (g_j,...,g_m)]</i> takes the name <i>R</i> of the original table, a pair of table name <i>S</i> and a set of column names <i>s_i</i> as specification of the first partition and optionally a second pair <i>T</i> , (<i>g_j</i> ,..., <i>g_m</i>) as specification of the second partition [4]. Thus, this SMO includes the consecutive execution of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the SMO <i>CREATE_{table}</i> operator, needed to create the new table(s) <i>S</i> (and <i>T</i>, if applicable), followed by • the corresponding DMO <i>INSERT_{row}</i> operations, needed to populate the new tables <i>S</i> (and <i>T</i>, if applicable) with the rows in the source table <i>R</i>, and finished with • the SMO <i>DROP_{table}</i> operator used to remove the source table <i>R</i>. 	53

¹ See template's discussion.

Identifier SMO Pattern 1 (SMOPI) ADD_{table}

Syntax

CREATE TABLE $R(c_1, \dots, c_n)$

Semantics

A new table R is created. This operator takes a table name and a set of column definitions and creates an empty table with the specified name and schema [4].

Key elements

<i>User</i>	The database user who performs the schema modification operator ADD_{table} .
<i>SMO Operator</i>	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by creating a new table.
<i>Database schema</i>	The database schema which is evolved. <i>Source schema version</i> (V_j) The schema version before the execution of the ADD_{table} . <i>Target schema version</i> (V_{j+1}) The schema version after the execution of the ADD_{table} .
<i>Table</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through three different elements: <i>Table name</i> (R_{name}) The name of the table to be created. <i>Target table</i> (R) The new table created in the <i>target schema version</i> . <i>Previous table</i> (P_i) Each table P_i represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> .
<i>Column</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through two different elements: <i>Column's definition</i> (c_{kdef}) Each c_{kdef} represents the definition of a column of the table to be created. <i>Target table's column</i> (c_k) Each c_k represents a column in the <i>target table</i> .

Database context

SMO involved element	SMO ID	Rationale
<i>User</i>	User 1	The database user who performs the schema modification operator ADD_{table} . <i>Note:</i> for the sake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 7.
<i>SMO Operator</i>	CREATE _{table} 2	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by creating a new table.
<i>Table name</i>	R_{name} 3	The name of the table to be created.
<i>Column's definition</i>	c_{kdef} 4	The definition of the columns of the table to be created.
<i>Source schema version</i>	V_j 5	The schema version before the execution of the ADD_{table} .
<i>Target schema version</i>	V_{j+1} 6	The schema version after the execution of the ADD_{table} .
<i>Target table</i>	R 7	The new table created in the <i>target schema version</i> .
<i>Target table's column</i>	c_k 8	The columns in the <i>target table</i> .
<i>Previous table</i>	P_i 9	Each table P_i represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> . <i>Note:</i> for the sake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 7.

2
3 4
Syntax: CREATE TABLE R ($c_{1def}, \dots, c_{ndef}$)

Figure 7. Representation that models the semantics of *SMOP1*

Mapping to PROV

Figure 8. PROV template defined to represent semantics of *SMOP1* (Figure 7)

PROV elements

SMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
User 1	prov:Agent 1 / var:user	The User 1 bears the responsibility for the execution of the CREATE_{table} 2. To reflect this fact, the User 1 is mapped to a prov:Agent identified by var:user.
CREATE_{table} 2	prov:Activity 2 / var:smo	The CREATE_{table} 2 represents that the execution of an operator has taken place. Such an execution is a prov:Activity with the identifier var:smo.
R_{name} 3	prov:Entity 3 / var:inputTableName	R_{name} 3 is a prov:Entity identified by var:inputTableName.
c_{kdef} 4	prov:Entity 4 / var:inputColumnDef	c_{kdef} 4 is a prov:Entity identified by var:inputColumnDef.
V_j 5	prov:Entity 5 / var:sourceSchema	V_j 5 is a prov:Entity identified by var:sourceSchema.
V_{j+1} 6	prov:Entity 6 / var:targetSchema	V_{j+1} 6 is a prov:Entity identified by var:targetSchema.
R 7	prov:Entity 7 / var:targetTable	R 7 is a prov:Entity identified by var:targetTable.
c_k 8	prov:Entity 8 / var:targetColumn	Each column c_k 8 in the <i>target table</i> is mapped to a separate prov:Entity with the identifier var:targetColumn.
P_i 9	prov:Entity 9 / var:previousTable	Each table P_i 9 in the <i>target schema version</i> , inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> , is mapped to a separate prov:Entity with the identifier var:previousTable.

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:smo 2	prov:type / var:operatorName	The value var:operatorName is the name of the operation var:smo 2.
	o2p:instruction / var:operationInstruction	The value var:operationInstruction is the expression of the operation var:smo 2.
	o2p:executed / var:executed	The value var:executed refers to whether the operator var:smo 2 has been executed or rolled back.
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:smo 2.
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:endTransTime	The var:endTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:smo 2.
var:inputTableName 5	prov:value / var:inTableName	The value var:inTableName is the name of the table to be created.
var:inputColumnDef 4	sch2p:columnName /	The value is the name of a column to be added to var:targetTable 7.
	sch2p:typeName /	The value is the string with the type of a column to be added to var:targetTable 7.

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:sourceSchema 5	prov:type / sch2p:schema	The value sch2p:schema shows that var:sourceSchema 5 is a database schema version.
	sch2p:schemaName / var:sSchemaName	The value var:sSchemaName is the string with the name of the database schema var:sourceSchema 5 .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:ssEndTransTime	The var:ssEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:sourceSchema 5 .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:ssEndValidTime	The var:ssEndValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid end time of var:sourceSchema 5 .
var:targetSchema 6	prov:type / sch2p:schema	The value sch2p:schema shows that var:targetSchema 6 is a database schema version.
	sch2p:schemaName / var:tSchemaName	The value var:tSchemaName is the string with the name of the database schema var:targetSchema 6 .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:tsStartTransTime	The var:tsStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetSchema 6 .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:tsStartValidTime	The var:tsStartValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetSchema 6 .
var:targetTable 7	prov:type / sch2p:table	The value sch2p:table shows that var:targetTable 7 is a table.
	sch2p:tableName / var:tTableName	The value var:tTableName is the string with the name of the table var:targetTable 7 .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:ttStartTransTime	The var:ttStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetTable 7 .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:ttStartValidTime	The var:ttStartValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetTable 7 .
var:targetColumn 8	prov:type / sch2p:column	The value sch2p:column shows that var:targetColumn 8 is a column.
	sch2p:typeName / var:tColumnType	The value var:tColumnType is the string with the type of var:targetColumn 8 .
	sch2p:columnName / var:tColumnName	The value var:tColumnName is the string with the name of the column var:targetColumn 8 .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:tcStartTransTime	The var:tcStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetColumn 8 .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:tcStartValidTime	The var:tcStartValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetColumn 8 .
	bitemp:linked / var:inputColumnDef	Attribute needed to avoid incorrect cartesian product among var:targetColumn 8 elements and var:inputColumnDef 4 elements when template instantiation [10].
var:previousTable 9	prov:type / sch2p:table	The value sch2p:table shows that var:previousTable 9 is a table.
	sch2p:tableName / var:pTableName	The value var:pTableName is the string with the name of the table var:previousTable 9 .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a <code>prov:wasAssociatedWith</code>	It is the assignment of responsibility to <code>var:user</code> for <code>var:smo</code> .
b <code>prov:used</code>	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:inputColumnDef</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
c <code>prov:used</code>	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:inputTableName</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
d <code>prov:wasInvalidatedBy</code>	It shows that <code>var:sourceSchema</code> is not longer available for use .
e <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetSchema</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
f <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetTable</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
g <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetColumn</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
h <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:targetTable</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
i <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:targetColumn</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
j <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:previousTable</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
k <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the update of <code>var:sourceSchema</code> resulting in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
l <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the update of <code>var:inputTableName</code> resulting in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
m <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the update of <code>var:inputColumnDef</code> resulting in <code>var:targetColumn</code> .

Discussion

- The *key elements table* and *column* participate in the syntax and semantics through different elements each; as operator's parameter and as operator's result. On the one hand, *table* participates with (1) *table name*, as the name of the table taken as parameter (R_{name}), and (2) *target table*, as the created table (R), which includes the name of the table as attribute. On the other hand, *column* participates with (1) *column's definition*, as the definition of a column of the table to be created (c_{kdef}), and (2) *target table's column*, as a column in the *target table* (c_k), which, at the same time includes the information concerning the column's definition. Given that an operator might not be executed, we have decided to explicitly distinguish operator's parameters and operator's results and separately represent them in the PROV template, ensuring us to register at least the operator's parameters in case the operator execution finally does not take place.

Syntax

DROP TABLE R

Semantics

The table R is dropped. This operator takes only a single parameter, the name of the table to be dropped [4].

Key elements

<i>User</i>	The database user who performs the schema modification operator DEL_{table} .
<i>SMO Operator</i>	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by dropping the <i>source table</i> whose name is given as parameter.
<i>Database schema</i>	The database schema which is evolved. <i>Source schema version</i> (V_j) The schema version before the execution of the DEL_{table} . <i>Target schema version</i> (V_{j+1}) The schema version after the execution of the DEL_{table} .
<i>Table</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through three different elements: <i>Table name</i> (R_{name}) The name of the table to be dropped. <i>Source table</i> (R) The table of the <i>source schema version</i> to be dropped. <i>Previous table</i> (P_i) Each table P_i represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> .
<i>Column</i>	This element participates in the semantics through two different elements: <i>Source table's column</i> (c_k) Each c_k represents a column in the deleted <i>source table</i> . <i>Source column's value</i> (c_{vk}) Each c_{vk} represents a value of the <i>source table's column</i> .
<i>Primary key constraint</i>	This element participates in the semantics through the element: <i>Source PK constraint</i> (pk) It represents the primary key of the deleted <i>source table</i> (if any).

Database context

SMO involved element	SMO ID	Rationale
<i>User</i>	User 1	The database user who performs the schema modification operator DEL_{table} . <i>Note:</i> for the sake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 9.
<i>SMO Operator</i>	DEL_{table} 2	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>source schema version</i> by dropping the <i>source table</i> whose name is given as parameter.
<i>Source table</i>	R 3	The table of the <i>source schema version</i> to be dropped.
<i>Source table's column</i>	c_k 4	Each column in the <i>source table</i> .
<i>Source column's value</i>	c_{vk} 5	Each c_{vk} represents a value of a <i>source table's column</i> .
<i>Source PK constraint</i>	pk 6	The primary key constraint of the <i>source table</i> .
<i>Source schema version</i>	V_j 7	The schema version before the execution of the DEL_{table} .
<i>Target schema version</i>	V_{j+1} 8	The schema version after the execution of the DEL_{table} .
<i>Previous table</i>	P_i 9	Each table P_i represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> . <i>Note:</i> for the sake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 9.

2

Syntax: *DROP TABLE R*

Figure 9. Representation that models the semantics of *SMOP2*

Mapping to PROV

Figure 10. PROV template defined to represent semantics of *SMOP2* (Figure 9)

PROV elements

SMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
User 1	<code>prov:Agent 1 /</code> <code>var:user</code>	The User 1 bears the responsibility for the execution of the <code>DEL_{table} 2</code> . To reflect this fact, the User 1 is mapped to a <code>prov:Agent</code> identified by <code>var:user</code> .
<code>DEL_{table} 2</code>	<code>prov:Activity 2 /</code> <code>var:smo</code>	The <code>DEL_{table} 2</code> represents that the execution of an operator has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:smo</code> .
R 3	<code>prov:Entity 3 /</code> <code>var:sourceTable</code>	R 3 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourceTable</code> .
c_k 4	<code>prov:Entity 4 /</code> <code>var:sourceColumn</code>	Each c_k 4 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourceColumn</code> .
c_{vk} 5	<code>prov:Entity 5 /</code> <code>var:sourceColumnValue</code>	Each value c_{vk} 5 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:sourceColumnValue</code> .
pk 6	<code>prov:Entity 6 /</code> <code>var:sourcePrimaryKey</code>	pk 6 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourcePrimaryKey</code> .
V_j 7	<code>prov:Entity 7 /</code> <code>var:sourceSchema</code>	V_j 7 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourceSchema</code> .
V_{j+1} 8	<code>prov:Entity 8 /</code> <code>var:targetSchema</code>	V_{j+1} 8 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
P_i 9	<code>prov:Entity 9 /</code> <code>var:previousTable</code>	Each table P_i 9 in the <i>target schema version</i> , inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> , is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:previousTable</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:smo 2	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>var:operatorName</code>	The value <code>var:operatorName</code> is the name of the operation var:smo 2.
	<code>o2p:instruction /</code> <code>var:operationInstruction</code>	The value <code>var:operationInstruction</code> is the expression of the operation var:smo 2.
	<code>o2p:executed /</code> <code>var:executed</code>	The value <code>var:executed</code> refers to whether the operator var:icmo 2 has been executed or rolled back.
	<code>bitemp:startTransTime /</code> <code>var:startTransTime</code>	The <code>var:startTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction start time of var:smo 2.
	<code>bitemp:endTransTime /</code> <code>var:endTransTime</code>	The <code>var:endTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction end time of var:smo 2.
var:sourceTable 3	<code>prov:type /</code> <code>sch2p:table</code>	The value <code>sch2p:table</code> shows that var:sourceTable 3 is a table.
	<code>sch2p:tableName /</code> <code>var:sTableName</code>	The value <code>var:sTableName</code> is the string with the name of the table var:sourceTable 3.
	<code>bitemp:endTransTime /</code> <code>var:stEndTransTime</code>	The <code>var:stEndTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction end time of var:sourceTable 3.
	<code>bitemp:endValidTime /</code> <code>var:stEndValidTime</code>	The <code>var:stEndValidTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the valid end time of var:sourceTable 3.

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:sourceColumn 4	prov:type / sch2p:column	The value sch2p:column shows that var:sourceColumn 4 is a table.
	sch2p:typeName / var:sColumnType	The value var:sColumnType is the string with the type of var:sourceColumn 4 .
	sch2p:columnName / var:sColumnName	The value var:sColumnName is the string with the name of the column var:targetColumn 4 .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:scEndTransTime	The var:scEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:sourceColumn 4 .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:endValidTime	The var:endValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid end time of var:sourceColumn 4 .
var:sourceColumnValue 5	prov:type / d2p:value	The value d2p:value shows that var:sourceColumnValue 5 is a data value.
	d2p:rowID / var:rowID	The var:rowID is the identifier of the tuple to which var:sourceColumnValue 5 belongs.
	d2p:columnValue / var:columnValue	The value var:columnValue is the direct representation of var:sourceColumnValue 5 .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:scvEndTransTime	The var:scvEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:sourceColumnValue 5 .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:scvEndValidTime	The var:scvEndValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid end time of var:sourceColumnValue 5 .
var:sourcePrimaryKey 6	prov:type / sch2p:pk	The value sch2p:pk shows that var:sourcePrimaryKey 6 is a primary key.
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:spkEndTransTime	The var:spkEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:sourcePrimaryKey 6 .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:spkEndValidTime	The var:spkEndValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid end time of var:sourcePrimaryKey 6 .
var:sourceSchema 7	prov:type / sch2p:schema	The value sch2p:schema shows that var:sourceSchema 7 is a database schema version.
	sch2p:schemaName / var:sSchemaName	The value var:sSchemaName is the string with the name of the database schema var:sourceSchema 7 .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:ssEndTransTime	The var:ssEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:sourceSchema 7 .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:ssEndValidTime	The var:ssEndValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid end time of var:sourceSchema 7 .
var:targetSchema 8	prov:type / sch2p:schema	The value sch2p:schema shows that var:targetSchema 8 is a database schema version.
	sch2p:schemaName / var:tSchemaName	The value var:tSchemaName is the string with the name of the database schema var:targetSchema 8 .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:ttStartTransTime	The var:ttStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetSchema 8 .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:ttStartValidTime	The var:ttStartValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetSchema 8 .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:previousTable is a table.		
	sch2p:tableName / var:tableName	The value var:tableName is the string with the name of the table var:previousTable .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
prov:wasAssociatedWith	It is the assignment of responsibility to var:user for var:smo.
prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:sourceTable by var:smo.
prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that var:sourceSchema is not longer available for use.
prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that var:sourceColumn is not longer available for use.
prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that var:sourceColumnValue is not longer available for use.
prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that var:sourcePrimaryKey is not longer available for use.
prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that var:sourceTable is not longer available for use.
prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:targetSchema by var:smo.
prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of var:sourceSchema resulting in var:targetSchema.
prov:hadMember	It states that var:previousTable is one of the elements in var:targetSchema.

Discussion

- Although the *key element table* participates in the syntax and semantics through two different elements: *table name*, as the name of the table taken as parameter (R_{name}), and *source table*, as the table to be dropped (R), we have identified both key elements as an only element in the PROV template, var:sourceTable represents the *source table* itself and contains, as attribute, the name of the table (var:sTableName).
- In this proposal, we have considered the *primary key constraint* among the different constraints a table can include, but more type of constraints can be considered. Our proposal can be easily extended to consider other types of constraints.

Syntax

ADD COLUMN *c* [AS *const* | *f*(*c*₁, ..., *c*_{*f*})] INTO *R*_{*i*}

Semantics

A new column *c* is added to an existing table *R*_{*i*}. This operator takes as parameters the name of the table, the column definition of the new column, and optionally, a constant or function. The resulting table is *R*_{*i*+1}. If a constant is provided, this operator takes such a value as the row's value for the new column *c* [3]. If a function is provided, this operator applies it to each row in *R*_{*i*} to calculate the row's value for the new column *c*. The function receives all other column values of the row as parameters [4]. Otherwise, if neither the constant nor the function is provided, it assigns 'null' as the row's value for the new column *c*. The columns, columns's values as well as constraints in *R*_{*i*} remain the same in *R*_{*i*+1}.

Key elements

<i>User</i>	The database user who performs the schema modification operator <i>ADD_{column}</i> .								
<i>SMO Operator</i>	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by adding a new column into the <i>source table</i> . It takes as parameters:								
	<table> <tr> <td><i>Table name</i> (<i>R_{name}</i>)</td> <td>See the <i>Table</i> element below.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Column definition</i> (<i>c_{def}</i>)</td> <td>See the <i>Column</i> element below.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Constant</i> (<i>const</i>) <i>Function</i> (<i>f</i>(<i>c</i>₁, ..., <i>c</i>_{<i>f</i>}))</td> <td>Either a constant or a function may be provided as parameter. The <i>constant</i> refers to the constant to be assigned as value of the new column to be added, while the <i>function</i> corresponds to the function to be applied to each row in the <i>source table</i> to calculate the row's value of the new column.</td> </tr> </table>	<i>Table name</i> (<i>R_{name}</i>)	See the <i>Table</i> element below.	<i>Column definition</i> (<i>c_{def}</i>)	See the <i>Column</i> element below.	<i>Constant</i> (<i>const</i>) <i>Function</i> (<i>f</i> (<i>c</i> ₁ , ..., <i>c</i> _{<i>f</i>}))	Either a constant or a function may be provided as parameter. The <i>constant</i> refers to the constant to be assigned as value of the new column to be added, while the <i>function</i> corresponds to the function to be applied to each row in the <i>source table</i> to calculate the row's value of the new column.		
<i>Table name</i> (<i>R_{name}</i>)	See the <i>Table</i> element below.								
<i>Column definition</i> (<i>c_{def}</i>)	See the <i>Column</i> element below.								
<i>Constant</i> (<i>const</i>) <i>Function</i> (<i>f</i> (<i>c</i> ₁ , ..., <i>c</i> _{<i>f</i>}))	Either a constant or a function may be provided as parameter. The <i>constant</i> refers to the constant to be assigned as value of the new column to be added, while the <i>function</i> corresponds to the function to be applied to each row in the <i>source table</i> to calculate the row's value of the new column.								
<i>Database schema</i>	The database schema which is evolved.								
	<table> <tr> <td><i>Source schema version</i> (<i>V_j</i>)</td> <td>The schema version before the execution of the <i>ADD_{column}</i>.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Target schema version</i> (<i>V_{j+1}</i>)</td> <td>The schema version after the execution of the <i>ADD_{column}</i>.</td> </tr> </table>	<i>Source schema version</i> (<i>V_j</i>)	The schema version before the execution of the <i>ADD_{column}</i> .	<i>Target schema version</i> (<i>V_{j+1}</i>)	The schema version after the execution of the <i>ADD_{column}</i> .				
<i>Source schema version</i> (<i>V_j</i>)	The schema version before the execution of the <i>ADD_{column}</i> .								
<i>Target schema version</i> (<i>V_{j+1}</i>)	The schema version after the execution of the <i>ADD_{column}</i> .								
<i>Table</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through three different elements:								
	<table> <tr> <td><i>Table name</i> (<i>R_{name}</i>)</td> <td>The name of the table to which the new column is being added.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Source table</i> (<i>R_i</i>)</td> <td>The table of the <i>source schema version</i> to which the new column is being added.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Target table</i> (<i>R_{i+1}</i>)</td> <td>The resulting table in the <i>target schema version</i> after adding the <i>new column</i>.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Previous table</i> (<i>P_i</i>)</td> <td>Each table <i>P_i</i> represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i>.</td> </tr> </table>	<i>Table name</i> (<i>R_{name}</i>)	The name of the table to which the new column is being added.	<i>Source table</i> (<i>R_i</i>)	The table of the <i>source schema version</i> to which the new column is being added.	<i>Target table</i> (<i>R_{i+1}</i>)	The resulting table in the <i>target schema version</i> after adding the <i>new column</i> .	<i>Previous table</i> (<i>P_i</i>)	Each table <i>P_i</i> represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> .
<i>Table name</i> (<i>R_{name}</i>)	The name of the table to which the new column is being added.								
<i>Source table</i> (<i>R_i</i>)	The table of the <i>source schema version</i> to which the new column is being added.								
<i>Target table</i> (<i>R_{i+1}</i>)	The resulting table in the <i>target schema version</i> after adding the <i>new column</i> .								
<i>Previous table</i> (<i>P_i</i>)	Each table <i>P_i</i> represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> .								
<i>Column</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through four different elements:								
	<table> <tr> <td><i>Column definition</i> (<i>c_{def}</i>)</td> <td>The definition of the column to be added to the <i>source table</i>.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>New column</i> (<i>c</i>)</td> <td>The column added to <i>target table</i>.</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td><i>New column's value</i> (<i>c_{v_l}</i>) Each <i>c_{v_l}</i> represents a value of the new <i>new column</i>.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Previous column</i> (<i>c_k</i>)</td> <td>Each <i>c_k</i> represents a column in the <i>target table</i>, inherited from the <i>source table</i>.</td> </tr> </table>	<i>Column definition</i> (<i>c_{def}</i>)	The definition of the column to be added to the <i>source table</i> .	<i>New column</i> (<i>c</i>)	The column added to <i>target table</i> .		<i>New column's value</i> (<i>c_{v_l}</i>) Each <i>c_{v_l}</i> represents a value of the new <i>new column</i> .	<i>Previous column</i> (<i>c_k</i>)	Each <i>c_k</i> represents a column in the <i>target table</i> , inherited from the <i>source table</i> .
<i>Column definition</i> (<i>c_{def}</i>)	The definition of the column to be added to the <i>source table</i> .								
<i>New column</i> (<i>c</i>)	The column added to <i>target table</i> .								
	<i>New column's value</i> (<i>c_{v_l}</i>) Each <i>c_{v_l}</i> represents a value of the new <i>new column</i> .								
<i>Previous column</i> (<i>c_k</i>)	Each <i>c_k</i> represents a column in the <i>target table</i> , inherited from the <i>source table</i> .								
<i>Primary key constraint</i>	This element participates in the semantics through the element:								
	<i>Previous PK constraint</i> (<i>pk</i>) It represents the primary key of the <i>target table</i> , inherited from the <i>source table</i> (if any).								

Database context

SMO involved element	SMO ID	Rationale
User	User 1	The database user who performs the schema modification operator ADD_{column} . <i>Note:</i> for the sake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 11.
SMO Operator	ADD_{column} 2	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>source schema version</i> by adding a new column into the <i>source table</i> .
Column definition	c_{def} 3	The definition of the column to be added to the <i>source table</i> .
Constant Function	$const \mid f(c_1, \dots, c_f)$ 4	It refers to the constant to be assigned as value of the <i>new column</i> or to the function to be applied to each row in <i>source table</i> to calculate the row's value of the <i>new column</i> . They are optional and excluding.
Source table	R_i 5	The table of the <i>source schema version</i> to which the <i>column definition</i> is being added.
Source schema version	V_j 6	The schema version before the execution of the ADD_{column} .
Target schema version	V_{j+1} 7	The schema version after the execution of the ADD_{column} .
Target table	R_{i+1} 8	The resulting table in the <i>target schema version</i> after adding the <i>new column</i> .
New column	c 9	The new column added to the <i>target table</i> .
New column's value	c_{vj} 10	Each c_{vj} represents a value of the new <i>new column</i> .
Previous column	c_k 11	Each column c_k represents a column in the <i>target table</i> inherited from the <i>source table</i> .
Previous PK constraint	pk 12	pk represents the <i>primary key constraint</i> of the <i>target table</i> inherited from the <i>source table</i> (if any).
Previous table	P_i 13	Each table P_i represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> . <i>Note:</i> for the sake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Representation that models the semantics of SMOP3

Mapping to PROV

Figure 12. PROV template defined to represent semantics of *SMOP3* (Figure 11)

PROV elements

SMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
User 1	<code>prov:Agent 1 /</code> <code>var:user</code>	The User 1 bears the responsibility for the execution of the <code>ADD_{column}</code> 2. To reflect this fact, the User 1 is mapped to a <code>prov:Agent</code> identified by <code>var:user</code> .
<code>ADD_{column}</code> 2	<code>prov:Activity 2 /</code> <code>var:smo</code>	The <code>ADD_{column}</code> 2 represents that the execution of an operator has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:smo</code> .
<code>c_{def}</code> 3	<code>prov:Entity 3 /</code> <code>var:inputColumnDef</code>	<code>c_{def}</code> 3 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:inputColumnDef</code> .
<code>const f(c₁,...,c_f)</code> 4	<code>prov:Entity 4 /</code> <code>var:inputConstOrFunc</code>	Either <code>const</code> or <code>f(c₁,...,c_f)</code> (if provided) 4 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:inputConstOrFunc</code> .
<code>R_i</code> 5	<code>prov:Entity 5 /</code> <code>var:sourceTable</code>	<code>R_i</code> 5 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourceTable</code> .
<code>V_j</code> 6	<code>prov:Entity 6 /</code> <code>var:sourceSchema</code>	<code>V_j</code> 6 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourceSchema</code> .

PROV elements

SMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
V_{j+1} is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetSchema</code> .		
R_{i+1} is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetTable</code> .		
c is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:newColumn</code> .		
c_{vl} is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:newColumnValue</code> .		
c_k in the <i>target table</i> inherited from the <i>source table</i> , is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:previousColumn</code> .		
pk in the <i>target table</i> , inherited from the <i>source table</i> , is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:previousPrimaryKey</code> .		
P_i in the <i>target schema version</i> , inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> , is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:previousTable</code> .		

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
<code>var:smo</code> .		
	<code>o2p:instruction</code> / <code>var:operationInstruction</code>	The value <code>var:operationInstruction</code> is the expression of the operation <code>var:icmo</code> .
	<code>o2p:executed</code> / <code>var:executed</code>	The value <code>var:executed</code> refers to whether the operator <code>var:smo</code> has been executed or rolled back.
	<code>bitemp:startTransTime</code> / <code>var:startTransTime</code>	The <code>var:startTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction start time of <code>var:smo</code> .
	<code>bitemp:endTransTime</code> / <code>var:endTransTime</code>	The <code>var:endTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction end time of <code>var:smo</code> .
<code>var:inputColumnDef</code> .		
	<code>sch2p:typeName</code> / <code>var:inColumnType</code>	The value <code>var:inColumnType</code> is the string with the type of the column to be added to <code>var:sourceTable</code> .
<code>var:inputConstOrFunc</code> .		
<code>var:sourceTable</code> is a table.		
	<code>sch2p:tableName</code> / <code>var:sTableName</code>	The value <code>var:sTableName</code> is the string with the name of the table <code>var:sourceTable</code> .
	<code>bitemp:endTransTime</code> / <code>var:stEndTransTime</code>	The <code>var:stEndTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction end time of <code>var:sourceTable</code> .
	<code>bitemp:endValidTime</code> / <code>var:stEndValidTime</code>	The <code>var:stEndValidTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the valid end time of <code>var:sourceTable</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:sourceSchema is a database schema version.		
	sch2p:schemaName / var:sSchemaName	The value var:sSchemaName is the string with the name of the database schema var:sourceSchema .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:ssEndTransTime	The SSis an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:sourceSchema .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:ssEndValidTime	The var:ssEndValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid end time of var:sourceSchema .
var:targetSchema is a database schema version.		
	sch2p:schemaName / var:tSchemaName	The value var:tSchemaName is the string with the name of the database schema var:targetSchema .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:tsStartTransTime	The var:tsStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetSchema .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:tsStartValidTime	The var:tsStartValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetSchema .
var:targetTable is a table.		
	sch2p:tableName / var:tTableName	The value var:tTableName is the string with the name of the table var:targetTable .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:ttStartTransTime	The var:ttStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetTable .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:ttStartValidTime	The var:ttStartValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetTable .
var:newColumn is a table.		
	sch2p:typeName / var:nColumnType	The value var:nColumnType is the string with the type of var:newColumn .
	sch2p:columnName / var:nColumnName	The value var:nColumnName is the string with the name of the column var:newColumn .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:ncStartTransTime	The var:ncStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:newColumn .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:ncStartValidTime	The var:ncStartValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:newColumn .
var:newColumnValue is a data value.		
	d2p:rowID / var:rowID	The var:rowID is the identifier of the row to which var:newColumnValue belongs.
	d2p:columnValue / var:columnValue	The value var:columnValue is the direct representation of var:newColumnValue .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:ncvStartTransTime	The var:ncvStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:newColumnValue .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:ncvStartValidTime	The var:ncvStartValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:newColumnValue .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:previousColumn is a table.		
	sch2p:columnName / var:pColumnName	The value var:pColumnName is the string with the name of the column var:previousColumn .
var:previousPrimaryKey is a primary key.		
var:previousTable is a table.		
	sch2p:tableName / var:pTableName	The value var:pTableName is the string with the name of the table var:previousTable .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
prov:wasAssociatedWith	It is the assignment of responsibility to var:user for var:smo.
prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:inputColumnDef by var:smo.
prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:inputConstOrFunc by var:smo.
prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing var:sourceTable by var:smo.
prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that var:sourceSchema is not longer available for use.
prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that var:sourceTable is not longer available for use.
prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:targetSchema by var:smo.
prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:targetTable by var:smo.
prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:newColumn by var:smo.
prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of var:newColumnValue by var:smo.
prov:hadMember	It states that var:targetTable is one of the elements in var:targetSchema.
prov:hadMember	It states that var:newColumn is one of the elements in var:targetTable.
prov:hadMember	It states that var:previousTable is one of the elements in var:targetSchema.
prov:hadMember	It states that var:previousColumn is one of the elements in var:targetTable.
prov:hadMember	It states that var:previousPrimaryKey is one of the elements in var:targetTable.
prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of var:sourceSchema resulting in var:targetSchema.
prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of var:sourceTable resulting in var:targetTable.
prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of var:inputColumnDef resulting in var:newColumn.
prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of var:inputConstOrFunc resulting in var:newColumnValue.
prov:specializationOf	var:newColumnValue is a specialization of var:newColumn.

Discussion

- The *key element column* participates in the syntax and semantics through different elements each; as operator's parameter and as operator's result. More specifically, *column* participates with (1) *column's definition*, as the definition of the column to be added to the *source table* (c_{def}), and (2) *new column*, as the column added to the *target table* (c), which, at the same time, includes the information concerning the column's definition. Given that an operator might not be executed, we have decided to explicitly distinguish operator's parameters and operator's results and separately represent them in the PROV template, ensuring us to register at least the operator's parameters in case the operator execution finally does not take place. In the case of *table*, it participates with (1) *table name*, as the name of the table taken as parameter (R_{name}), and (2) *source table*, as

the table to which the new column is being added (R_i). However, it maintains a difference with respect to the *key elements column*, and it is that *source table* not only includes the information regarding the name of the table, but it also does not depend on the successful execution of the operation. For this reason, we have decided not to represent the *table name* in the PROV template as an independent *entity*.

- A question that might arise is why in Figure 12 `var:previousColumn` (the table version before the application of the operator) representing the previous columns of the table. We have made this decision because a table that acts as a `var:sourceTable` in the application of a SMO operator, was a `var:targetTable` in a previous operator's application. Thus, the columns associated to such a table in a `var:sourceTable` were registered when it previously played the role of `var:targetTable`.
- Another aspect to register would be the columns' values involved in the calculation of the values of the new column c when using a *function*. Our proposal can be easily extended to register such information.

Syntax

COPY TABLE *T* INTO *R*

Semantics

A new table *R* is created as a duplicate of table *T*. The new additional table *R* is created with the same structure as the source table *T*. Additionally, this new table *R* should also contain the same data as the source table *T* [11].

Thus, this SMO includes the consecutive execution of:

- the SMO *CREATE_{table}* operator, needed to create the new table *R*, followed by
- the corresponding DMO *INSERT_{row}* operation, needed to populate the new table *R* with the rows in the source table *T*.

Key elements

<i>User</i>	The database user who performs the schema modification operator <i>COPY_{table}</i> , and, consequently, the schema modification operator <i>CREATE_{table}</i> and the data modification operation <i>INSERT_{row}</i> .
<i>SMO Operator</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through two different elements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>SMO Copy table</i> The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by duplicating a table. It takes as parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Source table name (T_{name})</i> See the <i>Table</i> element below. <i>Target table name (R_{name})</i> See the <i>Table</i> element below. <i>SMO Create table</i> The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by creating a table and which is executed as a consequence of the execution of the <i>SMO Copy table</i>.
<i>DMO Insert row</i>	The data modification operation executed to populate the new table and which is executed as a consequence of the execution of the <i>SMO Copy table</i> .
<i>Database schema</i>	The database schema which is evolved. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Source schema version (V_j)</i> The schema version before the execution of the <i>COPY_{table}</i>. <i>Target schema version (V_{j+1})</i> The schema version after the execution of the <i>COPY_{table}</i>.
<i>Table</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through five different elements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Source table name (T_{name})</i> The name of the table taken as source to be duplicated. <i>Target table name (R_{name})</i> The name of the table to be created in the <i>target schema version</i>. <i>Source table (T)</i> The table in the <i>source schema version</i> taken as source to be duplicated. <i>Target table (R)</i> The new table created in the <i>target schema version</i>. <i>Previous table (P_i)</i> Each table <i>P_i</i> represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i>.
<i>Column</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through four different elements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Source table's column (c_k)</i> Each column <i>c_k</i> represents a column of the <i>source table T</i>. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Source column's value (c_{vk})</i> Each <i>c_{vk}</i> represents a value in a <i>column c_k</i> of the <i>source table T</i>. <i>Target table's column (g_k)</i> Each <i>g_k</i> represents a column of the <i>target table R</i> which, at the same time, is a copy of column <i>c_k</i> of the <i>source table T</i>. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Target column's value (g_{vk})</i> Each <i>g_{vk}</i> represents a value in a <i>column g_k</i> of the <i>target table R</i> which, at the same time, is a copy of value <i>c_{vk}</i> of column <i>c_k</i> of the <i>source table T</i>.

Database context

SMO involved element	SMO ID	Rationale
User	User 1	The database user who performs the schema modification operator $COPY_{table}$. <i>Note:</i> for the sake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 13.
SMO Copy table	$COPY_{table}$ 2	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by duplicating a table.
Source table	T 3	The table in the <i>source schema version</i> taken as source to be duplicated.
Target table name	R_{name} 4	The name of the table to be created in the <i>target schema version</i> .
Source schema version	V_j 5	The schema version before the execution of the $COPY_{table}$.
Target schema version	V_{j+1} 6	The schema version after the execution of the $COPY_{table}$.
Source table's column	c_k 7	Each column c_k represents a column in the <i>source table T</i> .
Source column's value	c_{vk} 8	Each c_{kvalue} represents a value in a column c_k of the <i>source table T</i> .
Target table	R 9	The new table created in the <i>target schema version</i> .
Target table's column	g_k 10	Each g_k represents a column of the <i>target table R</i> .
Target column's value	g_{vk} 11	Each g_{vk} represents a value in a column g_k of the <i>target table R</i> .
Previous table	P_i 12	Each table P_i represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> . <i>Note:</i> for the sake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 13.
SMO Create table	$CREATE_{table}$ 13	The schema modification operator whose application is derived from the execution of the <i>SMO Copy table</i> . <i>Note:</i> since this operator is implicit to the execution of the main operator $COPY_{table}$ 2 , we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 13.
DMO Insert row	$INSERT_{row}$ 14	The data modification operation whose application is derived from the execution of the <i>SMO Copy table</i> . <i>Note:</i> since this operator is implicit to the execution of the main operator $COPY_{table}$ 2 , we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Representation that models the semantics of *SMOP4*

Mapping to PROV

Figure 14. PROV template defined to represent semantics of *SMOP4* (Figure 13)

PROV elements

SMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
User 1	<code>prov:Agent 1 /</code> <code>var:user</code>	The User 1 bears the responsibility for the execution of the $COPY_{table}$ 2. To reflect this fact, the User 1 is mapped to a <code>prov:Agent</code> identified by <code>var:user</code> .
$COPY_{table}$ 2	<code>prov:Activity 2 /</code> <code>var:smo</code>	The $COPY_{table}$ 2 represents that the execution of an operator has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:smo</code> .
T 3	<code>prov:Entity 3 /</code> <code>var:sourceTable</code>	T 3 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourceTable</code> .
R_{name} 4	<code>prov:Entity 4 /</code> <code>var:targetTableName</code>	R_{name} 4 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetTableName</code> .
V_j 5	<code>prov:Entity 5 /</code> <code>var:sourceSchema</code>	V_j 5 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourceSchema</code> .
V_{j+1} 6	<code>prov:Entity 6 /</code> <code>var:targetSchema</code>	V_{j+1} 6 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
c_k 7	<code>prov:Entity 7 /</code> <code>var:sourceColumn</code>	Each column c_k 7 in the <i>source table</i> is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:sourceColumn</code> .
c_{vk} 8	<code>prov:Entity 8 /</code> <code>var:sourceColumnValue</code>	Each value c_{vk} 8 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:sourceColumnValue</code> .
R 9	<code>prov:Entity 9 /</code> <code>var:targetTable</code>	R 9 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetTable</code> .

PROV elements

SMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
g_k in the <i>target table</i> is mapped to a separate prov:Entity with the identifier <code>var:targetColumn</code> .		
g_{vk} is a separate prov:Entity with the identifier <code>var:targetColumnValue</code> .		
P_i in the <i>target schema version</i> , inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> , is mapped to a separate prov:Entity with the identifier <code>var:previousTable</code> .		
$CREATE_{table}$ represents that the execution of the CREATE TABLE operator has taken place. Such an execution is a prov:Activity with the identifier <code>var:smoCT</code> .		
$INSERT_{row}$ represents that the execution of the INSERT ROW operation has taken place. Such an execution is a prov:Activity with the identifier <code>var:dmoI</code> .		

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description	
<code>var:smo</code> .			
	o2p:instruction / <code>var:operationInstruction</code>	The value <code>var:operationInstruction</code> is the expression of the operation <code>var:smo</code> .	
	o2p:executed / <code>var:executed</code>	The value <code>var:executed</code> refers to whether the operator <code>var:smo</code> has been executed or rolled back.	
	bitemp:startTransTime / <code>var:startTransTime</code>	The <code>var:startTransTime</code> is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of <code>var:smo</code> .	
	bitemp:endTransTime / <code>var:endTransTime</code>	The <code>var:endTransTime</code> is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of <code>var:smo</code> .	
<code>var:sourceTable</code> is a table.			
	sch2p:tableName / <code>var:tableName</code>	The value <code>var:tableName</code> is the string with the name of the table <code>var:sourceTable</code> .	
<code>var:targetTableName</code>	prov:value / <code>var:tableName</code>	The value <code>var:targetTableName</code> is the name of the table to be created.	
	<code>var:sourceSchema</code> is a database schema version.		
		sch2p:schemaName / <code>var:schemaName</code>	The value <code>var:schemaName</code> is the string with the name of the database schema <code>var:sourceSchema</code> .
		bitemp:endTransTime / <code>var:endTransTime</code>	The <code>var:endTransTime</code> is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of <code>var:sourceSchema</code> .
<code>var:sourceSchema</code> .			

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:targetSchema 6	prov:type / sch2p:schema	The value <code>sch2p:schema</code> shows that var:targetSchema 6 is a database schema version.
	sch2p:schemaName / var:schemaName	The value var:schemaName is the string with the name of the database schema var:targetSchema 6 .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction start time of var:targetSchema 6 .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:startValidTime	The var:startValidTime is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the valid start time of var:targetSchema 6 .
var:sourceColumn 7	sch2p:columnName / var:columnName	The value var:columnName is the name of a column of var:sourceTable 8 .
	sch2p:typeName / var:columnType	The value var:columnType is the string with the type of a column of var:sourceTable 8 .
var:sourceColumnValue 8	prov:type / d2p:value	The value <code>d2p:value</code> shows that var:sourceColumnValue 8 is a data value.
	d2p:rowID / var:rowID	The var:rowID is the identifier of the row to which var:sourceColumnValue 8 belongs.
	d2p:columnValue / var:columnValue	The value var:columnValue is the direct representation of var:sourceColumnValue 8 .
var:targetTable 9	prov:type / sch2p:table	The value <code>sch2p:table</code> shows that var:targetTable 9 is a table.
	sch2p:tableName / var:tableName	The value var:tableName is the string with the name of the table var:targetTable 9 .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction start time of var:targetTable 9 .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:startValidTime	The var:startValidTime is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the valid start time of var:targetTable 9 .
var:targetColumn 10	prov:type / sch2p:column	The value <code>sch2p:column</code> shows that var:targetColumn 10 is a table.
	sch2p:typeName / var:columnType	The value var:columnType is the string with the type of var:targetColumn 10 .
	sch2p:columnName / var:columnName	The value var:columnName is the string with the name of the column var:targetColumn 10 .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction start time of var:targetColumn 10 .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:startValidTime	The var:startValidTime is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the valid start time of var:targetColumn 10 .
	bitemp:linked / var:inputColumnDef	Attribute needed to avoid incorrect cartesian product among var:targetColumn 10 elements and var:sourceColumn 7 elements when template instantiation [10].

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:targetColumnValue is a data value.		
	d2p:rowID / var:rowID	The var:rowID is the identifier of the row to which var:targetColumnValue belongs.
	d2p:columnValue / var:columnValue	The value var:columnValue is the direct representation of var:targetColumnValue .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetColumnValue .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:startValidTime	The var:startValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetColumnValue .
	bitemp:linked / var:column	Attribute needed to avoid incorrect cartesian product among varTargetColumnValue elements when template instantiation [10].
	bitemp:linked / var:value	Attribute needed to avoid incorrect cartesian product among var:targetColumnValue elements when template instantiation [10].
var:previousTable is a table.		
	sch2p:tableName / var:tableName	The value var:tableName is the string with the name of the table var:previousTable .
var:smoCT .		
	o2p:instruction / var:ctOperationInstruction	The value var:ctOperationInstruction is the expression of the operation var:smoCT .
	o2p:executed / var:ctExecuted	The value var:ctExecuted refers to whether the operator var:smoCT has been executed or rolled back.
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:ctStartTransTime	The var:ctStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:smoCT .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:ctEndTransTime	The var:ctEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:smoCT .
var:dmoI .		
	o2p:instruction / var:iOperationInstruction	The value var:iOperationInstruction is the expression of the operation var:dmoI .
	o2p:executed / var:iExecuted	The value var:iExecuted refers to whether the operator var:dmoI has been executed or rolled back.
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:iStartTransTime	The var:iStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:dmoI .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:iEndTransTime	The var:iEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:dmoI .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a <code>prov:wasAssociatedWith</code>	It is the assignment of responsibility to <code>var:user</code> for <code>var:smo</code> .
b <code>prov:used</code>	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:sourceTable</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
c <code>prov:used</code>	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:targetTableName</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
d <code>prov:wasInvalidatedBy</code>	It shows that <code>var:sourceSchema</code> is not longer available for use.
e <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetSchema</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
f <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetTable</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
g <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetColumn</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
h <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetColumnValue</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
i <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:targetTable</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
j <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:targetColumn</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
k <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:previousTable</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
l <code>prov:specializationOf</code>	<code>var:targetColumnValue</code> is a specialization of <code>var:targetColumn</code> .
m <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the update of <code>var:sourceSchema</code> resulting in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
n <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the update of <code>var:sourceTable</code> resulting in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
o <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the update of <code>var:sourceColumn</code> resulting in <code>var:targetColumn</code> .
p <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the update of <code>var:sourceColumnValue</code> resulting in <code>var:targetColumnValue</code> .
q <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the update of <code>var:targetTableName</code> resulting in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
r <code>prov:wasInformedBy</code>	It shows that <code>var:smoCT</code> is informed by <code>var:smo</code> .
s <code>prov:wasInformedBy</code>	It shows that <code>var:dmoI</code> is informed by <code>var:smo</code> .

Discussion

- The *key element table* particularly participates with (1) *target table name*, as the name of the table to be created as a duplicate of the *source table* (R_{name}), and (2) *target table*, as the created table (R), which includes the name of the *target table* as attribute. Given that an operator might not be executed, we have decided to explicitly distinguish operator's parameters and operator's results and separately represent them in the PROV template, ensuring us to register at least the operator's parameters in case the operator execution finally does not take place.
- The *key element table* also participates in the syntax and semantics through other two different elements: *source table name*, as the name of the table taken as source to be duplicated (T_{name}), and *source table*, as the duplicated table (T), which includes the name of the *source table* as attribute. However, it maintains a difference with respect to the previous case, and it is that *source table* not only includes the information regarding the name of the table, but it also does not depend on the successful execution of the operation. For this reason, we have decided not to represent the *source table name* in the PROV template as an independent entity.

Syntax

MERGE TABLE *S, T* INTO *R*

Semantics

A new table *R* is created as the result of merging two given tables *S* and *T* along the row dimension, removing the original tables [4]. More specifically, this operator unions tuples of two tables into a target table. This operator takes as parameters the names of the original tables and the name of the resulting table [4].

The schema of the source tables is not required to be equivalent since, in case both schemas differ, the target table contains 'null' values in the corresponding cells [4]. Thus, in this case, columns' values of the target table could come from either one of two source tables or from both.

The operator 'eliminates duplicates' in *R*, that is, in case *S* and *T* contain equivalent rows, these rows will show up only once in *R*.

Thus, this SMO includes the consecutive execution of:

- the SMO *CREATE_{table}* operator, needed to create the new table *R*, followed by
- the corresponding DMO *INSERT_{row}* operation, needed to populate the new table *R* with the rows in the source tables *S* and *T*, and finished with
- the SMO *DROP_{table}* operator used to remove the source tables *S* and *T*.

Key elements

<i>User</i>	The database user who performs the schema modification operator <i>MERGE_{table}</i> , and, consequently, the schema modification operator <i>CREATE_{table}</i> , the data modification operation <i>INSERT_{row}</i> , and the schema modification operator <i>DROP_{table}</i> .												
<i>SMO Operator</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through three different elements: <table> <tr> <td><i>SMO Merge table</i></td> <td>The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by merging two tables into another table. It takes as parameters: <table> <tr> <td><i>Source table name (S_{name})</i></td> <td>See the <i>Table</i> element below.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Source table name (T_{name})</i></td> <td>See the <i>Table</i> element below.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Target table name (R_{name})</i></td> <td>See the <i>Table</i> element below.</td> </tr> </table> </td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>SMO Create table</i></td> <td>The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by creating a table and which is executed as a consequence of the execution of the <i>SMO Merge table</i>.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>SMO Drop table</i></td> <td>The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by dropping a table and which is executed as a consequence of the execution of the <i>SMO Merge table</i>.</td> </tr> </table>	<i>SMO Merge table</i>	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by merging two tables into another table. It takes as parameters: <table> <tr> <td><i>Source table name (S_{name})</i></td> <td>See the <i>Table</i> element below.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Source table name (T_{name})</i></td> <td>See the <i>Table</i> element below.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Target table name (R_{name})</i></td> <td>See the <i>Table</i> element below.</td> </tr> </table>	<i>Source table name (S_{name})</i>	See the <i>Table</i> element below.	<i>Source table name (T_{name})</i>	See the <i>Table</i> element below.	<i>Target table name (R_{name})</i>	See the <i>Table</i> element below.	<i>SMO Create table</i>	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by creating a table and which is executed as a consequence of the execution of the <i>SMO Merge table</i> .	<i>SMO Drop table</i>	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by dropping a table and which is executed as a consequence of the execution of the <i>SMO Merge table</i> .
<i>SMO Merge table</i>	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by merging two tables into another table. It takes as parameters: <table> <tr> <td><i>Source table name (S_{name})</i></td> <td>See the <i>Table</i> element below.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Source table name (T_{name})</i></td> <td>See the <i>Table</i> element below.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Target table name (R_{name})</i></td> <td>See the <i>Table</i> element below.</td> </tr> </table>	<i>Source table name (S_{name})</i>	See the <i>Table</i> element below.	<i>Source table name (T_{name})</i>	See the <i>Table</i> element below.	<i>Target table name (R_{name})</i>	See the <i>Table</i> element below.						
<i>Source table name (S_{name})</i>	See the <i>Table</i> element below.												
<i>Source table name (T_{name})</i>	See the <i>Table</i> element below.												
<i>Target table name (R_{name})</i>	See the <i>Table</i> element below.												
<i>SMO Create table</i>	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by creating a table and which is executed as a consequence of the execution of the <i>SMO Merge table</i> .												
<i>SMO Drop table</i>	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by dropping a table and which is executed as a consequence of the execution of the <i>SMO Merge table</i> .												
<i>DMO Insert row</i>	The data modification operation executed to populate the new table and which is executed as a consequence of the execution of the <i>SMO Merge table</i> .												
<i>Database schema</i>	The database schema which is evolved. <table> <tr> <td><i>Source schema version (V_j)</i></td> <td>The schema version before the execution of the <i>MERGE_{table}</i>.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Target schema version (V_{j+1})</i></td> <td>The schema version after the execution of the <i>MERGE_{table}</i>.</td> </tr> </table>	<i>Source schema version (V_j)</i>	The schema version before the execution of the <i>MERGE_{table}</i> .	<i>Target schema version (V_{j+1})</i>	The schema version after the execution of the <i>MERGE_{table}</i> .								
<i>Source schema version (V_j)</i>	The schema version before the execution of the <i>MERGE_{table}</i> .												
<i>Target schema version (V_{j+1})</i>	The schema version after the execution of the <i>MERGE_{table}</i> .												
<i>Table</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through five different elements: <table> <tr> <td><i>Source table name (S_{name}, T_{name})</i></td> <td>The name of each table taken as source to be merged.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Target table name (R_{name})</i></td> <td>The name of the table to be created in the <i>target schema version</i>.</td> </tr> <tr> <td><i>Source table (S, T)</i></td> <td>Each table in the <i>source schema version</i> taken as source to be merged.</td> </tr> </table>	<i>Source table name (S_{name}, T_{name})</i>	The name of each table taken as source to be merged.	<i>Target table name (R_{name})</i>	The name of the table to be created in the <i>target schema version</i> .	<i>Source table (S, T)</i>	Each table in the <i>source schema version</i> taken as source to be merged.						
<i>Source table name (S_{name}, T_{name})</i>	The name of each table taken as source to be merged.												
<i>Target table name (R_{name})</i>	The name of the table to be created in the <i>target schema version</i> .												
<i>Source table (S, T)</i>	Each table in the <i>source schema version</i> taken as source to be merged.												

	<i>Target table</i> (R)	The new table created in the <i>target schema version</i> .
	<i>Previous table</i> (P_i)	Each table P_i represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> .
<i>Column</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through four different elements:	
	<i>Source table's column</i> (c_k)	Each column c_k represents a column of the <i>source table</i> S and/or T .
	<i>Source column's value</i> (c_{vk})	Each c_{vk} represents a value in a column c_k of the <i>source table</i> S and/or T .
	<i>Target table's column</i> (g_k)	Each g_k represents a column of the <i>target table</i> R which, at the same time, is a copy of column c_k of the <i>source table</i> S and/or T .
	<i>Target column's value</i> (g_{vk})	Each g_{vk} represents a value in a column g_k of the <i>target table</i> R which, at the same time, is either a copy of value c_{vk} of column c_k of the <i>source table</i> S and/or T , or a 'null' value.

Database context

SMO involved element	SMO ID	Rationale
<i>User</i>	User 1	The database user who performs the schema modification operator $MERGE_{table}$. <i>Note:</i> for the sake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 15.
<i>SMO Merge table</i>	$MERGE_{table}$ 2	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by merging two tables into another table.
<i>Source table</i>	S, T 3	Each table in the <i>source schema version</i> taken as source to be merged.
<i>Target table name</i>	R_{name} 4	The name of the table to be created in the <i>target schema version</i> .
<i>Source schema version</i>	V_j 5	The schema version before the execution of the $MERGE_{table}$.
<i>Target schema version</i>	V_{j+1} 6	The schema version after the execution of the $MERGE_{table}$.
<i>Source table's column</i>	c_k 7	Each column c_k represents a column in the <i>source table</i> S and/or T .
<i>Source column's value</i>	c_{vk} 8	Each c_{kvalue} represents a value in a column c_k of the <i>source table</i> S and/or T .
<i>Target table</i>	R 9	The new table created in the <i>target schema version</i> .
<i>Target table's column</i>	g_k 10	Each g_k represents a column of the <i>target table</i> R .
<i>Target column's value</i>	g_{vk} 11	Each g_{vk} represents a value in a column g_k of the <i>target table</i> R .
<i>Previous table</i>	P_i 12	Each table P_i represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> . <i>Note:</i> for the sake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 15.

SMO involved element	SMO ID	Rationale
<i>SMO Create table</i>	$CREATE_{table}$	The schema modification operator whose application is derived from the execution of the <i>SMO Merge table</i> . <i>Note:</i> since this operator is implicit to the execution of the main operator $MERGE_{table}$, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 15.
<i>DMO Insert row</i>	$INSERT_{row}$	The data modification operation whose application is derived from the execution of the <i>SMO Merge table</i> . <i>Note:</i> since this operator is implicit to the execution of the main operator $MERGE_{table}$, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 15.
<i>SMO Drop table</i>	DEL_{table}	The schema modification operator whose application is derived from the execution of the <i>SMO Merge table</i> . <i>Note:</i> since this operator is implicit to the execution of the main operator $MERGE_{table}$, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Representation that models the semantics of *SMOP5*

Mapping to PROV

Figure 16. PROV template defined to represent semantics of SMOP5 (Figure 15)

PROV elements

SMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
User 1	<code>prov:Agent 1 /</code> <code>var:user</code>	The User 1 bears the responsibility for the execution of the $MERGE_{table}$ 2. To reflect this fact, the User 1 is mapped to a <code>prov:Agent</code> identified by <code>var:user</code> .
$MERGE_{table}$ 2	<code>prov:Activity 2 /</code> <code>var:smo</code>	The $MERGE_{table}$ 2 represents that the execution of an operator has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:smo</code> .
S, T 3	<code>prov:Entity 3 /</code> <code>var:sourceTable</code>	Each S, T 3 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourceTable</code> .
R_{name} 4	<code>prov:Entity 4 /</code> <code>var:targetTableName</code>	R_{name} 4 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetTableName</code> .
V_j 5	<code>prov:Entity 5 /</code> <code>var:sourceSchema</code>	V_j 5 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourceSchema</code> .
V_{j+1} 6	<code>prov:Entity 6 /</code> <code>var:targetSchema</code>	V_{j+1} 6 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetSchema</code> .

PROV elements

SMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
c_k 7	<code>prov:Entity</code> 7 / <code>var:sourceColumn</code>	Each column c_k 7 in a <i>source table</i> is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:sourceColumn</code> .
c_{vk} 8	<code>prov:Entity</code> 8 / <code>var:sourceColumnValue</code>	Each value c_{vk} 8 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:sourceColumnValue</code> .
R 9	<code>prov:Entity</code> 9 / <code>var:targetTable</code>	R 9 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetTable</code> .
g_k 10	<code>prov:Entity</code> 10 / <code>var:targetColumn</code>	Each column g_k 10 in the <i>target table</i> is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:targetColumn</code> .
g_{vk} 11	<code>prov:Entity</code> 11 / <code>var:targetColumnValue</code>	Each value g_{vk} 11 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:targetColumnValue</code> .
P_i 12	<code>prov:Entity</code> 12 / <code>var:previousTable</code>	Each table P_i 12 in the <i>target schema version</i> , inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> , is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:previousTable</code> .
$CREATE_{table}$ 13	<code>prov:Activity</code> 13 / <code>var:smoCT</code>	The $CREATE_{table}$ 13 represents that the execution of the CREATE TABLE operator has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:smoCT</code> .
$INSERT_{row}$ 14	<code>prov:Activity</code> 14 / <code>var:dmoI</code>	The $INSERT_{row}$ 14 represents that the execution of the INSERT ROW operation has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:dmoI</code> .
DEL_{table} 15	<code>prov:Activity</code> 15 / <code>var:smoDT</code>	The DEL_{table} 15 represents that the execution of the DROP TABLE operator has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:smoDT</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
<code>var:smo</code> 2	<code>prov:type</code> / <code>var:operatorName</code>	The value <code>var:operatorName</code> is the name of the operation <code>var:smo</code> 2.
	<code>o2p:instruction</code> / <code>var:operationInstruction</code>	The value <code>var:operationInstruction</code> is the expression of the operation <code>var:smo</code> 2.
	<code>o2p:executed</code> / <code>var:executed</code>	The value <code>var:executed</code> refers to whether the operator <code>var:smo</code> 2 has been executed or rolled back.
	<code>bitemp:startTransTime</code> / <code>var:startTransTime</code>	The <code>var:startTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction start time of <code>var:smo</code> 2.
	<code>bitemp:endTransTime</code> / <code>var:endTransTime</code>	The <code>var:endTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction end time of <code>var:smo</code> 2.
<code>var:sourceTable</code> 3	<code>prov:type</code> / <code>sch2p:table</code>	The value <code>sch2p:table</code> shows that <code>var:sourceTable</code> 3 is a table.
	<code>sch2p:tableName</code> / <code>var:tableName</code>	The value <code>var:tableName</code> is the string with the name of the table <code>var:sourceTable</code> 3.
	<code>bitemp:endTransTime</code> / <code>var:stEndTransTime</code>	The <code>var:stEndTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction end time of <code>var:sourceTable</code> 3.
	<code>bitemp:endValidTime</code> / <code>var:stEndValidTime</code>	The <code>var:stEndValidTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the valid end time of <code>var:sourceTable</code> 3.
<code>var:targetTableName</code> 4	<code>prov:value</code> / <code>var:tableName</code>	The value <code>var:targetTableName</code> is the name of the table to be created.

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:sourceSchema is a database schema version.		
	sch2p:schemaName / var:schemaName	The value var:schemaName is the string with the name of the database schema var:sourceSchema .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:endTransTime	The var:endTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:sourceSchema .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:endValidTime	The var:endValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid end time of var:sourceSchema .
var:targetSchema is a database schema version.		
	sch2p:schemaName / var:schemaName	The value var:schemaName is the string with the name of the database schema var:targetSchema .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetSchema .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:startValidTime	The var:startValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetSchema .
var:sourceColumn .		
	sch2p:columnName / var:columnName	The value var:columnName is the name of a column of var:sourceTable .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:scEndTransTime	The var:scEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:sourceColumn .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:endValidTime	The var:endValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid end time of var:sourceColumn .
var:sourceColumnValue is a data value.		
	d2p:rowID / var:rowID	The var:rowID is the identifier of the row to which var:sourceColumnValue belongs.
	d2p:columnValue / var:columnValue	The value var:columnValue is the direct representation of var:sourceColumnValue .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:scvEndTransTime	The var:scvEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:sourceColumnValue .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:scvEndValidTime	The var:scvEndValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid end time of var:sourceColumnValue .
var:targetTable is a table.		
	sch2p:tableName / var:tableName	The value var:tableName is the string with the name of the table var:targetTable .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetTable .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:startValidTime	The var:startValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetTable .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:targetColumn is a table.		
	sch2p:typeName / var:columnType	The value var:columnType is the string with the type of var:targetColumn .
	sch2p:columnName / var:columnName	The value var:columnName is the string with the name of the column var:targetColumn .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetColumn .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:startValidTime	The var:startValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetColumn .
	bitemp:linked / var:inputColumnDef	Attribute needed to avoid incorrect cartesian product among var:targetColumn elements when template instantiation [10].
	var:targetColumnValue	prov:type / d2p:value
d2p:rowID / var:rowID		The var:rowID is the identifier of the row to which var:targetColumnValue belongs.
d2p:duplicatedRowValue / var:duplicated		The var:duplicated refers to whether the var:targetColumnValue corresponds to a row that is duplicated in the source tables.
d2p:columnValue / var:columnValue		The value var:columnValue is the direct representation of var:targetColumnValue .
bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime		The var:startTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetColumnValue .
bitemp:startValidTime / var:startValidTime		The var:startValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetColumnValue .
bitemp:linked / var:column		Attribute needed to avoid incorrect cartesian product among var:targetColumnValue elements when template instantiation [10].
bitemp:linked / var:value		Attribute needed to avoid incorrect cartesian product among var:targetColumnValue elements when template instantiation [10].
var:previousTable is a table.		
	sch2p:tableName / var:tableName	The value var:tableName is the string with the name of the table var:previousTable .
var:smoCT .		
	o2p:instruction / var:ctOperationInstruction	The value var:ctOperationInstruction is the expression of the operation var:smoCT .
	o2p:executed / var:ctExecuted	The value var:ctExecuted refers to whether the operator var:smoCT has been executed or rolled back.
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:ctStartTransTime	The var:ctStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:smoCT .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:ctEndTransTime	The var:ctEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:smoCT .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:dmoI .		
	o2p:instruction / var:iOperationInstruction	The value var:iOperationInstruction is the expression of the operation var:dmoI .
	o2p:executed / var:iExecuted	The value var:iExecuted refers to whether the operator var:dmoI has been executed or rolled back.
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:iStartTransTime	The var:iStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:dmoI .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:iEndTransTime	The var:iEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:dmoI .
	var:smoDT	prov:type / var:dtOperatorName
o2p:instruction / var:dtOperationInstruction		The value var:dtOperationInstruction is the expression of the operation var:smoDT .
o2p:executed / var:dtExecuted		The value var:dtExecuted refers to whether the operator var:smoDT has been executed or rolled back.
bitemp:startTransTime / var:dtStartTransTime		The var:dtStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:smoDT .
bitemp:endTransTime / var:dtEndTransTime		The var:dtEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:smoDT .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a prov:wasAssociatedWith	It is the assignment of responsibility to <code>var:user</code> for <code>var:smo</code> .
b prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:sourceTable</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
c prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:targetTableName</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
d prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that <code>var:sourceSchema</code> is not longer available for use.
e prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that <code>var:sourceTable</code> is not longer available for use.
f prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that <code>var:sourceColumn</code> is not longer available for use.
g prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that <code>var:sourceColumnValue</code> is not longer available for use.
h prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetSchema</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
i prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetTable</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
j prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetColumn</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
k prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetColumnValue</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
l prov:hadMember	It states that <code>var:targetTable</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
m prov:hadMember	It states that <code>var:targetColumn</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
n prov:hadMember	It states that <code>var:previousTable</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
o prov:specializationOf	<code>var:targetColumnValue</code> is a specialization of <code>var:targetColumn</code> .
p prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of <code>var:sourceSchema</code> resulting in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
q prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of <code>var:sourceTable</code> resulting in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
r prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of <code>var:sourceColumn</code> resulting in <code>var:targetColumn</code> .
s prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of <code>var:sourceColumnValue</code> resulting in <code>var:targetColumnValue</code> .
t prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of <code>var:targetTableName</code> resulting in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
u prov:wasInformedBy	It shows that <code>var:smoCT</code> is informed by <code>var:smo</code> .
v prov:wasInformedBy	It shows that <code>var:dmoI</code> is informed by <code>var:smo</code> .
w prov:wasInformedBy	It shows that <code>var:smoDT</code> is informed by <code>var:smo</code> .

Discussion

- The *key element table* particularly participates with (1) *target table name*, as the name of the table to be created as the result of merging two given tables S and T (R_{name}), and (2) *target table*, as the created table (R), which includes the name of the *target table* as attribute. Given that an operator might not be executed, we have decided to explicitly distinguish operator's parameters and operator's results and separately represent them in the PROV template, ensuring us to register at least the operator's parameters in case the operator execution finally does not take place.
- The *key element table* also participates in the syntax and semantics through other two different elements: *source table name*, as the name of the tables taken as source to be duplicated (S_{name} and T_{name}), and *source table*, as the merged tables (S and T), which includes the name of the corresponding *source table* as attribute. However, it maintains a difference with respect to the previous case, and it is that *source table* not only includes the information regarding the name of the corresponding source table(s), but it also does not depend on the successful execution of the operation. For this reason, we have decided not to represent the *source table name* in the PROV template as an independent entity.
- The *key element column* particularly participates with *source table's column* (c_k), which represents a column of the *source table* S and/or T :
 - In case the source tables have exactly the same number of columns with the same types, that is, the same signature, each *source table's column* belongs to both *source tables*. In this case, each column of the *target table* (g_k) is a copy of column c_k of both, the *source table* S and the *source table* T . Equivalently, each column value c_{vk} of the *target table* comes from the corresponding column value c_{vk} of both *source tables*.

This situation covers semantics included in references such as [3, 12, 13, 14], which consider that the source tables must have the same signature.

- In case the schema of the source tables differs, each column of the *target table* (g_k) is a copy of column c_k belonging either to both *source tables* S and T , or to just one *source table*. Additionally, each column value c_{vk} of the *target table* comes from the corresponding column value c_{vk} of both source tables, of one of the source tables, or corresponds to the 'null' value.
- Other trends state that the source tables can be optionally removed [3]. In case source tables are not removed, the operator DEL_{table} will not be executed, and the PROV relation `prov:wasInvalidatedBy` between `var:smo` (operator DEL_{table}) and elements `var:sourceTable`, `var:sourceColumn` and `var:sourceColumnValue`, respectively, will not take place.

Syntax

`DECOMPOSE TABLE R INTO S (gi,...,gn) [, T (gj,...,gm)]`

Semantics

A table *R* is partitioned vertically into two (or one) tables *S* and *T* and then it is removed.

More specifically, `DECOMPOSE TABLE R INTO S (gi,...,gn) [, T, (gj,...,gm)]` takes the name *R* of the original table, a pair of table name *S* and a set of column names *s_i* as specification of the first partition and optionally a second pair *T*, (*g_j,...,g_m*) as specification of the second partition. If the second partition is not specified, *T* is not created [4].

This operator has generalized semantics, where the resulting partitioning is allowed to be incomplete and overlapping. The two sets of column definitions are independent. In case $S.C \cap T.C \neq \emptyset$, the columns $S.C \cap T.C$ are copied. In case $S.C \cup T.C \subset R.C$, the partitioning is incomplete [4].

Thus, this SMO includes the consecutive execution of:

- the SMO *CREATE_{table}* operator, needed to create the new table(s) *S* (and *T*, if applicable), followed by
- the corresponding DMO *INSERT_{row}* operations, needed to populate the new tables *S* (and *T*, if applicable) with the rows in the source table *R*, and finished with
- the SMO *DROP_{table}* operator used to remove the source table *R*.

Key elements

<i>User</i>	The database user who performs the schema modification operator <i>DECOMPOSE_{table}</i> , and, consequently, the schema modification operator <i>CREATE_{table}</i> , the data modification operation <i>INSERT_{row}</i> , and the schema modification operator <i>DROP_{table}</i> .
<i>SMO Operator</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through three different elements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>SMO Decompose table</i> The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by partitioning vertically a table into two (or one) tables. It takes as parameters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Source table name (R_{name})</i> See the <i>Table</i> element below. <i>Target table name (S_{name})</i> See the <i>Table</i> element below. <i>Target column name (g_{sname})</i> See the <i>Column</i> element below. <i>Target table name (T_{name})</i> If applicable. See the <i>Table</i> element below. <i>Target column name (g_{tname})</i> See the <i>Column</i> element below. <i>SMO Create table</i> The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by creating a table and which is executed as a consequence of the execution of the <i>SMO Decompose table</i>. <i>SMO Drop table</i> The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by dropping a table and which is executed as a consequence of the execution of the <i>SMO Decompose table</i>.
<i>DMO Insert row</i>	The data modification operation executed to populate the new table(s) and which is executed as a consequence of the execution of the <i>SMO Decompose table</i> .
<i>Database schema</i>	The database schema which is evolved. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Source schema version (V_j)</i> The schema version before the execution of the <i>DECOMPOSE_{table}</i>. <i>Target schema version (V_{j+1})</i> The schema version after the execution of the <i>DECOMPOSE_{table}</i>.

Table	<p>This element participates in the syntax and semantics through five different elements:</p> <p><i>Source table name</i> (R_{name}) The name of the table taken as source to be partitioned.</p> <p><i>Target table name</i> (S_{name}, T_{name}) The name of the table(s) to be created in the <i>target schema version</i>.</p> <p><i>Source table</i> (R) The table in the <i>source schema version</i> taken as source to be partitioned.</p> <p><i>Target table</i> (S, T) The new table(s) created in the <i>target schema version</i>.</p> <p><i>Previous table</i> (P_i) Each table P_i represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i>.</p>
Column	<p>This element participates in the syntax and semantics through five different elements:</p> <p><i>Source table's column</i> (c_k) Each column c_k represents a column of the <i>source table</i> R.</p> <p><i>Source column's value</i> (c_{vk}) Each c_{vk} represents a value in a column c_k of the <i>source table</i> R.</p> <p><i>Target column name</i> (g_{kname}) Each g_{kname} represents the definition of a column of the table(s) to be created.</p> <p><i>Target table's column</i> (g_k) Each g_k represents a column of the <i>target table</i> S (and T, if applicable) which, at the same time, is a copy of column c_k of the <i>source table</i> R.</p> <p><i>Target column's value</i> (g_{vk}) Each g_{vk} represents a value in a column g_k of the <i>target table</i> S (and T, if applicable) which, at the same time, is a copy of value c_{vk} of column c_k of the <i>source table</i> R.</p>

Database context

SMO involved element	SMO ID	Rationale
<i>User</i>	User 1	The database user who performs the schema modification operator $DECOMPOSE_{table}$. <i>Note:</i> for the sake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 17.
<i>SMO Decompose table</i>	$DECOMPOSE_{table}$ 2	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by decomposing a table into two (or one) tables.
<i>Source table</i>	R 3	The table in the <i>source schema version</i> taken as source to be decomposed.
<i>Target table name</i>	S_{name}, T_{name} 4	The name of the table(s) to be created in the <i>target schema version</i> .
<i>Target column name</i>	g_{kname} 5	The definition of the columns of the (s) to be created in the <i>target schema version</i> .
<i>Source schema version</i>	V_j 6	The schema version before the execution of the $DECOMPOSE_{table}$.
<i>Target schema version</i>	V_{j+1} 7	The schema version after the execution of the $DECOMPOSE_{table}$.
<i>Source table's column</i>	c_k 8	Each column c_k represents a column in the <i>source table</i> R .
<i>Source column's value</i>	c_{vk} 9	Each c_{kvalue} represents a value in a column c_k of the <i>source table</i> R .
<i>Target table</i>	S, T 10	The new table(s) created in the <i>target schema version</i> .
<i>Target table's column</i>	g_k 11	Each g_k represents a column of the <i>target table</i> S (and T , if applicable)
<i>Target column's value</i>	g_{vk} 12	Each g_{vk} represents a value in a column g_k of the <i>target table</i> S (and T , if applicable).
<i>Previous table</i>	P_i 13	Each table P_i represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> . <i>Note:</i> for the sake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 17.

SMO involved element	SMO ID	Rationale
<i>SMO Create table</i>	$CREATE_{table}$	The schema modification operator whose application is derived from the execution of the <i>SMO Decompose table</i> . <i>Note:</i> since this operator is implicit to the execution of the main operator , we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 17.
<i>DMO Insert row</i>	$INSERT_{row}$	The data modification operation whose application is derived from the execution of the <i>SMO Decompose table</i> . <i>Note:</i> since this operator is implicit to the execution of the main operator $DECOMPOSE_{table}$, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 17.
<i>SMO Drop table</i>	DEL_{table}	The schema modification operator whose application is derived from the execution of the <i>SMO Decompose table</i> . <i>Note:</i> since this operator is implicit to the execution of the main operator $DECOMPOSE_{table}$, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 17.

Figure 17. Representation that models the semantics of *SMOP6*

Mapping to PROV

Figure 18. PROV template defined to represent semantics of *SMOP6* (Figure 17)

PROV elements

SMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
User 1	<code>prov:Agent 1 / var:user</code>	The User 1 bears the responsibility for the execution of the $DECOMPOSE_{table}$ 2. To reflect this fact, the User 1 is mapped to a <code>prov:Agent</code> identified by <code>var:user</code> .
$DECOMPOSE_{table}$ 2	<code>prov:Activity 2 / var:smo</code>	The $DECOMPOSE_{table}$ 2 represents that the execution of an operator has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:smo</code> .
R 3	<code>prov:Entity 3 / var:sourceTable</code>	R 3 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourceTable</code> .
S_{name}, T_{name} 4	<code>prov:Entity 4 / var:targetTableName</code>	Each S_{name}, T_{name} 4 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetTableName</code> .
g_{kname} 5	<code>prov:Entity 5 / var:targetColumnName</code>	Each g_{kname} 5 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetColumnName</code> .
V_j 6	<code>prov:Entity 6 / var:sourceSchema</code>	V_j 6 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourceSchema</code> .
V_{j+1} 7	<code>prov:Entity 7 / var:targetSchema</code>	V_{j+1} 7 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetSchema</code> .

PROV elements

SMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
c_k 8	<code>prov:Entity</code> 8 / <code>var:sourceColumn</code>	Each column c_k 8 in a <i>source table</i> is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:sourceColumn</code> .
c_{vk} 9	<code>prov:Entity</code> 9 / <code>var:sourceColumnValue</code>	Each value c_{vk} 9 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:sourceColumnValue</code> .
R 10	<code>prov:Entity</code> 10 / <code>var:targetTable</code>	R 10 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetTable</code> .
g_k 11	<code>prov:Entity</code> 11 / <code>var:targetColumn</code>	Each column g_k 11 in the <i>target table</i> is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:targetColumn</code> .
g_{vk} 12	<code>prov:Entity</code> 12 / <code>var:targetColumnValue</code>	Each value g_{vk} 12 is a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:targetColumnValue</code> .
P_i 13	<code>prov:Entity</code> 13 / <code>var:previousTable</code>	Each table P_i 13 in the <i>target schema version</i> , inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> , is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:previousTable</code> .
$CREATE_{table}$ 14	<code>prov:Activity</code> 14 / <code>var:smoCT</code>	The $CREATE_{table}$ 14 represents that the execution of the CREATE TABLE operator has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:smoCT</code> .
$INSERT_{row}$ 15	<code>prov:Activity</code> 15 / <code>var:dmoI</code>	The $INSERT_{row}$ 15 represents that the execution of the INSERT ROW operation has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:dmoI</code> .
DEL_{table} 16	<code>prov:Activity</code> 16 / <code>var:smoDT</code>	The DEL_{table} 16 represents that the execution of the DROP TABLE operator has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:smoDT</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:smo 2	prov:type / var:operatorName	The value var:operatorName is the name of the operation var:smo 2 .
	o2p:instruction / var:operationInstruction	The value var:operationInstruction is the expression of the operation var:smo 2 .
	o2p:executed / var:executed	The value var:executed refers to whether the operator var:smo 2 has been executed or rolled back.
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:smo 2 .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:endTransTime	The var:endTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:smo 2 .
var:sourceTable 3	prov:type / sch2p:table	The value sch2p:table shows that var:sourceTable 3 is a table.
	sch2p:tableName / var:tableName	The value var:tableName is the string with the name of the table var:sourceTable 3 .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:stEndTransTime	The var:stEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:sourceTable 3 .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:stEndValidTime	The var:stEndValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid end time of var:sourceTable 3 .
var:targetTableName 4	prov:value / var:tableName	The value var:targetTableName is the name of the table to be created.
var:targetColumnName 5	sch2p:columnName / var:columnName	The value var:columnName is the name of a column of var:targetTable 9 .
var:sourceSchema 6	prov:type / sch2p:schema	The value sch2p:schema shows that var:sourceSchema 6 is a database schema version.
	sch2p:schemaName / var:schemaName	The value var:schemaName is the string with the name of the database schema var:sourceSchema 6 .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:endTransTime	The var:endTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:sourceSchema 6 .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:endValidTime	The var:endValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid end time of var:sourceSchema 6 .
var:targetSchema 7	prov:type / sch2p:schema	The value sch2p:schema shows that var:targetSchema 7 is a database schema version.
	sch2p:schemaName / var:schemaName	The value var:schemaName is the string with the name of the database schema var:targetSchema 7 .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetSchema 7 .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:startValidTime	The var:startValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetSchema 7 .
var:sourceColumn 8	sch2p:columnName / var:columnName	The value var:columnName is the name of a column of var:sourceTable 9 .
	sch2p:columnName / var:columnName	The value var:columnName is the string with the type of a column of var:sourceTable 9 .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:scEndTransTime	The var:scEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:sourceColumn 8 .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:endValidTime	The var:endValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid end time of var:sourceColumn 8 .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:sourceColumnValue is a data value.		
	d2p:rowID / var:rowID	The var:rowID is the identifier of the row to which var:sourceColumnValue belongs.
	d2p:columnValue / var:columnValue	The value var:columnValue is the direct representation of var:sourceColumnValue .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:scvEndTransTime	The var:scvEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:sourceColumnValue .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:scvEndValidTime	The var:scvEndValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid end time of var:sourceColumnValue .
var:targetTable is a table.		
	sch2p:tableName / var:tableName	The value var:tableName is the string with the name of the table var:targetTable .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetTable .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:startValidTime	The var:startValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetTable .
var:targetColumn is a table.		
	sch2p:columnName / var:columnName	The value var:columnName is the string with the name of the column var:targetColumn .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetColumn .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:startValidTime	The var:startValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetColumn .
	bitemp:linked / var:inputColumnDef	Attribute needed to avoid incorrect cartesian product among var:targetColumn elements when template instantiation [10].
var:targetColumnValue is a data value.		
	d2p:rowID / var:rowID	The var:rowID is the identifier of the row to which var:targetColumnValue belongs.
	d2p:columnValue / var:columnValue	The value var:columnValue is the direct representation of var:targetColumnValue .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:startTransTime	The var:startTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:targetColumnValue .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:startValidTime	The var:startValidTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the valid start time of var:targetColumnValue .
	bitemp:linked / var:column	Attribute needed to avoid incorrect cartesian product among var:targetColumnValue elements when template instantiation [10].
	bitemp:linked / var:value	Attribute needed to avoid incorrect cartesian product among var:targetColumnValue elements when template instantiation [10].

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:previousTable 15	prov:type / sch2p:table	The value sch2p:table shows that var:previousTable 15 is a table.
	sch2p:tableName / var:tableName	The value var:tableName is the string with the name of the table var:previousTable 15 .
var:smoCT 14	prov:type / var:ctOperatorName	The value var:ctOperatorName is the name of the operation var:smoCT 14 .
	o2p:instruction / var:ctOperationInstruction	The value var:ctOperationInstruction is the expression of the operation var:smoCT 14 .
	o2p:executed / var:ctExecuted	The value var:ctExecuted refers to whether the operator var:smoCT 14 has been executed or rolled back.
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:ctStartTransTime	The var:ctStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:smoCT 14 .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:ctEndTransTime	The var:ctEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:smoCT 14 .
var:dmoI 15	prov:type / var:iOperatorName	The value var:iOperatorName is the name of the operation var:dmoI 15 .
	o2p:instruction / var:iOperationInstruction	The value var:iOperationInstruction is the expression of the operation var:dmoI 15 .
	o2p:executed / var:iExecuted	The value var:iExecuted refers to whether the operator var:dmoI 15 has been executed or rolled back.
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:iStartTransTime	The var:iStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:dmoI 15 .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:iEndTransTime	The var:iEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:dmoI 15 .
var:smoDT 16	prov:type / var:dtOperatorName	The value var:dtOperatorName is the name of the operation var:smoDT 16 .
	o2p:instruction / var:dtOperationInstruction	The value var:dtOperationInstruction is the expression of the operation var:smoDT 16 .
	o2p:executed / var:dtExecuted	The value var:dtExecuted refers to whether the operator var:smoDT 16 has been executed or rolled back.
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:dtStartTransTime	The var:dtStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:smoDT 16 .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:dtEndTransTime	The var:dtEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:smoDT 16 .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a prov:wasAssociatedWith	It is the assignment of responsibility to <code>var:user</code> for <code>var:smo</code> .
b prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:sourceTable</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
c prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:targetTableName</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
d prov:used	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:targetColumnName</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
e prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that <code>var:sourceSchema</code> is not longer available for use.
f prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that <code>var:sourceTable</code> is not longer available for use.
g prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that <code>var:sourceColumn</code> is not longer available for use.
h prov:wasInvalidatedBy	It shows that <code>var:sourceColumnValue</code> is not longer available for use.
i prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetSchema</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
j prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetTable</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
k prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetColumn</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
l prov:wasGeneratedBy	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetColumnValue</code> by <code>var:smo</code> .
m prov:hadMember	It states that <code>var:targetTable</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
n prov:hadMember	It states that <code>var:targetColumn</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
o prov:hadMember	It states that <code>var:previousTable</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
p prov:specializationOf	<code>var:targetColumnValue</code> is a specialization of <code>var:targetColumn</code> .
q prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of <code>var:sourceSchema</code> resulting in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
r prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of <code>var:sourceTable</code> resulting in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
s prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of <code>var:sourceColumn</code> resulting in <code>var:targetColumn</code> .
t prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of <code>var:sourceColumnValue</code> resulting in <code>var:targetColumnValue</code> .
u prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of <code>var:targetTableName</code> resulting in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
v prov:wasDerivedFrom	It is the update of <code>var:targetColumnName</code> resulting in <code>var:targetColumn</code> .
w prov:wasInformedBy	It shows that <code>var:smoCT</code> is informed by <code>var:smo</code> .
x prov:wasInformedBy	It shows that <code>var:dmoI</code> is informed by <code>var:smo</code> .
y prov:wasInformedBy	It shows that <code>var:smoDT</code> is informed by <code>var:smo</code> .

Discussion

- The *key element table* particularly participates with (1) *target table name*, as the name of the table(s) to be created as a decomposition of the *source table* (S_{name}, T_{name}), and (2) *target table*, as the created table(s) (S, T), which includes the name of the *target table* as attribute. Given that an operator might not be executed, we have decided to explicitly distinguish operator's parameters and operator's results and separately represent them in the PROV template, ensuring us to register at least the operator's parameters in case the operator execution finally does not take place.
- The *key element table* also participates in the syntax and semantics through other two different elements: *source table name*, as the name of the table taken as source to be decomposed (R_{name}), and *source table*, as the decomposed table (R), which includes the name of the corresponding *source table* as attribute. However, it maintains a difference with respect to the previous case, and it is that *source table* not only includes the information regarding the name of the corresponding source table, but it also does not depend on the successful execution of the operation. For this reason, we have decided not to represent the *source table name* in the PROV template as an independent entity.
- The *key element column* particularly participates with (1) *target column name*, as the name of the columns to be created in the *target table* (g_{kname}) and (2) *target table's column*, as the created column (g_k), which includes the name of the *target table's column* as attribute. Given that an operator might not be executed, we have decided to explicitly distinguish operator's

parameters and operator's results and separately represent them in the PROV template, ensuring us to register at least the operator's parameters in case the operator execution finally does not take place.

- Other trends state that the source table can be optionally removed [3]. In case source table is not removed, the operator DEL_{table} will not be executed, and the PROV relation `prov:wasInvalidatedBy` between `var:smo` (operator DEL_{table}) and elements `var:sourceTable`, `var:sourceColumn` and `var:sourceColumnValue`, respectively, will not take place.
- Additional semantics for this operator are also considered by works such as [3], where it is stated that, in some situations, the insert statements used to populate the target table(s) are constrained by WHERE clauses whereby only a part of the original table R is decomposed. In these cases, table R is first partitioned horizontally, using the above-mentioned WHERE conditions. This situation is covered by the PROV template defined for the DMO $INSERT_{row}$, in particular, for the syntax: `INSERT INTO R (c_1, \dots, c_n) SELECT v_1, \dots, v_n FROM T [WHERE $cond$]` (see PROV template $DMOPI-INSERT_{row}$ in page 8).

6 ICMOs patterns

Pattern identifier	Semantics	Page
<i>ICMOPI</i>	<i>ADD_{primaryKey}</i> - A primary key constraint <i>pk</i> is added to a table <i>R_i</i> . This operator takes a table name and a set of column names and creates a primary key constraint <i>pk</i> on such columns. Depending on the number of column names included in such a set, the primary key will be created on a single column or on multiple columns.	64

Identifier ICMO Pattern 1 (ICMOPI) $ADD_{primaryKey}$

Syntax

$ALTER TABLE R_i ADD PRIMARY KEY pk(c_1, \dots, c_k) < policy >$

Semantics

A primary key constraint pk is added to a table R_i . This operator takes a table name and a set of column names and creates a primary key constraint pk on such columns. Depending on the number of column names included in such a set, the primary key will be created on a single column or on multiple columns.

The $< policy >$ place-holder is used as a selector to chose among the various integrity constraints enforcement policies [3]. Based on [3], we consider two enforcement policies:

- CHECK. When CHECK is used, the system verifies that the current database satisfies the new constraint pk . The ICMO operation is rolled back otherwise.
- ENFORCE. When ENFORCE is chosen, the system removes all tuples violating the newly introduced constraint pk : if a pair of tuples agrees on the key attributes but disagrees on any non-key attribute, then both tuples are removed.

Taking this into account, the operator is satisfactorily executed, and thus the primary key pk is created leading to the evolution of the schema, in the following cases:

- When the CHECK policy is chosen and the current database satisfies the new constraint pk .
- When the ENFORCE policy is chosen, either if there are tuples violating the constraint pk or not. In the first case, also such tuples are removed.

Key elements

<i>User</i>	The database user who performs the schema modification operator $ADD_{primaryKey}$.
<i>ICMO Operator</i>	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by adding a <i>primary key constraint</i> into the <i>source table</i> .
<i>Database schema</i>	The database schema which is evolved. <i>Source schema version</i> (V_j) The schema version before the execution of the <i>ICMO operator</i> $ADD_{primaryKey}$. <i>Target schema version</i> (V_{j+1}) The schema version after the execution of the <i>ICMO operator</i> $ADD_{primaryKey}$.
<i>Table</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through three different elements: <i>Table name</i> (R_{name}) The name of the table to which the <i>primary key constraint</i> is desired to be added. <i>Source table</i> (R_i) The table of the <i>source schema version</i> to which the <i>primary key constraint</i> is added. <i>Target table</i> (R_{i+1}) The resulting table in the <i>target schema version</i> after adding the <i>primary key constraint</i> . <i>Previous table</i> (P_i) Each table P_i represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> .
<i>Column</i>	This element participates in the syntax and semantics through three different elements: <i>PK Column's name</i> (c_{kname}) Each c_{kname} represents the name of a column in the <i>source table</i> on which the <i>primary key constraint</i> will be defined. <i>PK Column</i> (c_k) Each column c_k in the <i>source table</i> (also in the <i>target table</i>) on which the <i>primary key constraint</i> will be defined. <i>Previous column</i> (c_l) Each c_l represents a column in the <i>target table</i> , inherited from the <i>source table</i> .
<i>Primary key constraint</i>	This element participates in the semantics through the element: <i>PK constraint</i> (pk) It represents the primary key created in the <i>source table</i> .

Database context

ICMO's involved element	ICMO ID	Rationale
User	User 1	The database user who performs the schema modification operator $ADD_{primaryKey}$. <i>Note:</i> for the shake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 19.
ICMO Operator	$ADD_{primaryKey}$ 2	The schema modification operator whose application leads a change in the <i>database schema</i> by adding a primary key pk into the <i>source table</i> .
Source table	R_i 3	The table of the <i>source schema version</i> to which the <i>primary key constraint</i> is added.
PK Column	c_k 4	Each column in the <i>source table</i> (also in the <i>target table</i>) on which the <i>primary key constraint</i> will be defined.
Source schema version	V_j 5	The schema version before the execution of the $ADD_{primaryKey}$.
Target schema version	V_{j+1} 6	The schema version after the execution of the $ADD_{primaryKey}$.
Target table	R_{i+1} 7	The resulting table in the <i>target schema version</i> after adding the <i>primary key constraint</i> .
PK constraint	pk 8	The primary key constraint defined on the in the <i>target table</i> after the execution of the $ADD_{primaryKey}$.
Previous column	c_l 9	Each column c_l represents a column in the <i>target table</i> inherited from the <i>source table</i> .
Previous table	P_i 10	Each table P_i represents a table in the <i>target schema version</i> inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> . <i>Note:</i> for the shake of simplicity, we have decided not to depict this element in Figure 19.

Figure 19. Representation that models the semantics of $ICMOPI$

Figure 20. PROV template defined to represent semantics of ICMOPI (Figure 19)

PROV elements

ICMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
User 1	prov:Agent 1 / var:user	The User 1 bears the responsibility for the execution of the ADD _{primaryKey} 2. To reflect this fact, the User 1 is mapped to a prov:Agent identified by var:user.
ADD _{primaryKey} 2	prov:Activity 2 / var:icmo	The ADD _{primaryKey} 2 represents that the execution of an operator has taken place. Such an execution is a prov:Activity with the identifier var:icmo.
R _i 3	prov:Entity 3 / var:sourceTable	R _i 3 is a prov:Entity identified by var:sourceTable.

PROV elements

ICMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
c_k 4	<code>prov:Entity</code> 4 / <code>var:column</code>	Each column in c_k 4 is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:column</code> .
V_j 5	<code>prov:Entity</code> 5 / <code>var:sourceSchema</code>	V_j 5 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:sourceSchema</code> .
V_{j+1} 6	<code>prov:Entity</code> 6 / <code>var:targetSchema</code>	V_{j+1} 6 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
R_{i+1} 7	<code>prov:Entity</code> 7 / <code>var:targetTable</code>	R_{i+1} 7 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:targetTable</code> .
pk 8	<code>prov:Entity</code> 8 / <code>var:newPrimaryKey</code>	pk 8 is a <code>prov:Entity</code> identified by <code>var:newPrimaryKey</code> .
c_l 9	<code>prov:Entity</code> 9 / <code>var:column</code>	Each column c_l 9 in the <i>target table</i> inherited from the <i>source table</i> , is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:column</code> . Note that is represented in the same way that c_k , that is, each column in the <i>source table</i> (also in the <i>target table</i>) on which the <i>primary key constraint</i> will be defined.
P_i 10	<code>prov:Entity</code> 10 / <code>var:previousTable</code>	Each table P_i 10 in the <i>target schema version</i> , inherited from the <i>source schema version</i> , is mapped to a separate <code>prov:Entity</code> with the identifier <code>var:previousTable</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
<code>var:icmo</code> 2	<code>prov:type</code> / <code>var:operatorName</code>	The value <code>var:operatorName</code> is the name of the operation <code>var:icmo</code> 2.
	<code>prov:value</code> / <code>var:operatorText</code>	The value <code>var:operatorText</code> is the expression of the operation <code>var:icmo</code> 2.
	<code>o2p:policy</code> / <code>var:policy</code>	The value <code>var:policy</code> is the integrity constraint enforcement policy applied to the operator <code>var:icmo</code> 2.
	<code>o2p:executed</code> / <code>var:executed</code>	The value <code>var:executed</code> refers to whether the operator <code>var:icmo</code> 2 has been executed or rolled back.
	<code>o2p:instruction</code> / <code>var:operationInstruction</code>	The value <code>var:operationInstruction</code> is the expression of the operation <code>var:icmo</code> 2.
	<code>bitemp:startTransTime</code> / <code>var:startTransTime</code>	The <code>var:startTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction start time of <code>var:icmo</code> 2.
	<code>bitemp:endTransTime</code> / <code>var:endTransTime</code>	The <code>var:endTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction end time of <code>var:icmo</code> 2.
<code>var:sourceTable</code> 3	<code>prov:type</code> / <code>sch2p:table</code>	The value <code>sch2p:table</code> shows that <code>var:sourceTable</code> 3 is a table.
	<code>sch2p:tableName</code> / <code>var:sTableName</code>	The value <code>var:sTableName</code> is the string with the name of the table <code>var:sourceTable</code> 3.
	<code>bitemp:endTransTime</code> / <code>var:stEndTransTime</code>	The <code>var:stEndTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction end time of <code>var:sourceTable</code> 3.
	<code>bitemp:endValidTime</code> / <code>var:stEndValidTime</code>	The <code>var:stEndValidTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the valid end time of <code>var:sourceTable</code> 3.
<code>var:column</code> 4 9	<code>prov:type</code> / <code>sch2p:column</code>	The value <code>sch2p:column</code> shows that <code>var:column</code> 4 9 is a column.
	<code>sch2p:columnName</code> / <code>var:columnName</code>	The value <code>var:columnName</code> is the string with the name of the column <code>var:column</code> 4 9.

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:sourceSchema 5	prov:type / sch2p:schema	The value <code>sch2p:schema</code> shows that <code>var:sourceSchema</code> 5 is a database schema version.
	sch2p:schemaName / var:sSchemaName	The value <code>var:sSchemaName</code> is the string with the name of the database schema <code>var:sourceSchema</code> 5 .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:ssEndTransTime	The <code>var:ssEndTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction end time of <code>var:sourceSchema</code> 5 .
	bitemp:endValidTime / var:ssEndValidTime	The <code>var:ssEndValidTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the valid end time of <code>var:sourceSchema</code> 5 .
var:targetSchema 6	prov:type / sch2p:schema	The value <code>sch2p:schema</code> shows that <code>var:targetSchema</code> 6 is a database schema version.
	sch2p:schemaName / var:tSchemaName	The value <code>var:tSchemaName</code> is the string with the name of the database schema <code>var:targetSchema</code> 6 .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:tsStartTransTime	The <code>var:tsStartTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction start time of <code>var:targetSchema</code> 6 .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:tsStartValidTime	The <code>var:tsStartValidTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the valid start time of <code>var:targetSchema</code> 6 .
var:targetTable 7	prov:type / sch2p:table	The value <code>sch2p:table</code> shows that <code>var:targetTable</code> 7 is a table.
	sch2p:tableName / var:tTableName	The value <code>var:tTableName</code> is the string with the name of the table <code>var:targetTable</code> 7 .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:ttStartTransTime	The <code>var:ttStartTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction start time of <code>var:targetTable</code> 7 .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:ttStartValidTime	The <code>var:ttStartValidTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the valid start time of <code>var:targetTable</code> 7 .
var:newPrimaryKey 8	prov:type / sch2p:pk	The value <code>sch2p:pk</code> shows that <code>var:newPrimaryKey</code> 8 is a primary key.
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:npkStartTransTime	The <code>var:npkStartTransTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the transaction start time of <code>var:newPrimaryKey</code> 8 .
	bitemp:startValidTime / var:npkStartValidTime	The <code>var:npkStartValidTime</code> is an <code>xsd:dateTime</code> value for the valid start time of <code>var:newPrimaryKey</code> 8 .
var:previousTable 10	prov:type / sch2p:table	The value <code>sch2p:table</code> shows that <code>var:previousTable</code> 10 is a table.
	sch2p:tableName / var:pTableName	The value <code>var:pTableName</code> is the string with the name of the table <code>var:previousTable</code> 10 .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
a <code>prov:wasAssociatedWith</code>	It is the assignment of responsibility to <code>var:user</code> for <code>var:icmo</code> .
b <code>prov:used</code>	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:sourceTable</code> by <code>var:icmo</code> .
c <code>prov:used</code>	It is the beginning of utilizing <code>var:column</code> by <code>var:icmo</code> .
d <code>prov:wasInvalidatedBy</code>	It shows that <code>var:sourceSchema</code> is not longer available for use.
e <code>prov:wasInvalidatedBy</code>	It shows that <code>var:sourceTable</code> is not longer available for use.
f <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetSchema</code> by <code>var:icmo</code> .
g <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:targetTable</code> by <code>var:icmo</code> .
h <code>prov:wasGeneratedBy</code>	It is the completion of production of <code>var:newPrimaryKey</code> by <code>var:icmo</code> .
i <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:targetTable</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
j <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:newPrimaryKey</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
k <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:column</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:newPrimaryKey</code> .
l <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:previousTable</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
m <code>prov:hadMember</code>	It states that <code>var:column</code> is one of the elements in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
n <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the update of <code>var:sourceSchema</code> resulting in <code>var:targetSchema</code> .
o <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the update of <code>var:sourceTable</code> resulting in <code>var:targetTable</code> .
p <code>prov:wasDerivedFrom</code>	It is the update of <code>var:column</code> resulting in <code>var:newPrimaryKey</code> .

Discussion

- Although the *key element table* participates in the syntax and semantics through two different elements: *table* with (1) *table name*, as the name of the table taken as parameter (R_{name}), and (2) *source table*, as the table to which the *primary key constraint* is added (R_i), we have identified both key elements as an only element in the PROV template, `var:sourceTable` **3**. The main reason for this decision is that both elements do not depend on the operator execution and that `var:sourceTable` **3** represents the *source table* itself and contains, as attribute, the name of the table (`var:sTableName`).

Similarly happens with the *key element column* which participates in the syntax and semantics through the two elements (1) *PK Column's name*, as the names of the columns in the *source table* on which the *primary key constraint* will be defined (c_{kname}), and (2) *PK columns*, as the columns in the *source table* (also in the *target table*) on which the *primary key constraint* will be defined (c_k). We have also identified both elements as an only element in the PROV template (`var:column` **4**). More specifically, each column in c_k **4** is mapped to a separate `prov:Entity` with the identifier `var:column` **4**, which also contains the column name.

- When the ENFORCE policy is chosen and there are tuples violating the constraint pk , the DMO $DELETE_{row}$ operation is applied (see Figure 21). In this case, the pattern in Figure 20 is enriched with an activity `var:dmo` corresponding to such a $DELETE_{row}$ operation, together with the *PROV relation* `prov:wasInformedBy`, showing that such activity `var:dmo` is informed by the activity `var:smo` corresponding to the $ADD_{primaryKey}$ operator (see Figure 22). When executing both, the SMO $ADD_{primaryKey}$ operator and the DMO $DELETE_{row}$ operation, the corresponding bindings will be generated and, when expanding with the corresponding PROV templates (the corresponding to Figure 22 and the PROV Template of the DMO $DELETE_{row}$ operation), the resulting PROV documents will include the information of the chained operations.

Figure 21. Representation that models the semantics of *ICMOP1* with ENFORCE policy and tuples violating the pk

Figure 22. PROV template defined to represent semantics of *ICMOP1* (Figure 21)

PROV elements

ICMO ID	PROV / id	Rationale
$DELETE_{row}$ 11	<code>prov:Activity</code> 11 / <code>var:dmoD</code>	The $DELETE_{row}$ 11 represents that the execution of the operation DELETE ROW has taken place. Such an execution is a <code>prov:Activity</code> with the identifier <code>var:dmoD</code> .

Attributes

PROV Element	Attribute/Value	Description
var:dmoD .		
	o2p:executed / var:dExecuted	The value var:dExecuted refers to whether the operator var:dmoD has been executed or rolled back.
	o2p:instruction / var:dOperationInstruction	The value var:dOperationInstruction is the expression of the operation var:dmoD .
	bitemp:startTransTime / var:dStartTransTime	The var:dStartTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction start time of var:dmoD .
	bitemp:endTransTime / var:dEndTransTime	The var:dEndTransTime is an xsd:dateTime value for the transaction end time of var:dmoD .

PROV relations

PROV Relation	Description
prov:wasInformedBy	It shows that var:dmoD is informed by var:icmo.

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